

METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITY PRAGUE

BACHELOR'S DISSERTATION

2024

Karel Mařík

METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITY PRAGUE

International Relations and European Studies

BACHELOR'S DISSERTATION

**CZECHIA AND GERMANY'S APPROACHES
TO MARRIAGE EQUALITY: A
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS**

Author: Karel Mařík

Supervisor: Ing. Anna Gromilova, PhD.

2024

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am very thankful for all the help God provided me with throughout the writing of my Bachelor paper, because it felt very overwhelming at many times, even though the topic looks easy. I am very grateful also for the help from my Supervisor Ing. Anna Gromilova, Ph.D., her patience, and the valuable input she had throughout the writing process. I am very grateful also for my parents who helped me both financially to be able to concentrate more on writing this paper, and also for all their psychological support. I can't forget to thank my friend Emma Berg, who was so kind to always listen to me when I felt lost throughout the writing process and helped me not to lose track.

Last but not least, my friend Carolin Lomnasan was so kind to help interview Mr. Jürgen Klimke, and was the translator from German to English and vice-versa. Thanks to her, and thanks to Mr. Klimke, I was able to bring more valuable content to my Bachelor paper.

Regarding academic honesty, for this Bachelor paper, ChatGPT was used to translate the individual MPs' statements from Czech to English and from German to English, or certain papers or articles originally written in the German language (Kauder and Potrafke 2018; Kauder and Potrafke 2021; Fritzsche and Lang 2019; Spieker 2015) and these translations are used here. Other translations (for instance of some articles) were done via Google Translate (such as the section about Mr. Heribert Hirte).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
LIST OF TABLES	5
INTRODUCTION	1
1. TERMINOLOGY AND PARTY SUPPORT	4
1.1 Same-sex marriage	4
1.2 Registered partnership	4
1.3 LGBTQ	5
1.4 Parties and their stance on same-sex marriage	5
1.4.1 Czechia	5
1.4.2 Germany	7
2. METHODOLOGY, RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK	8
2.1 Methodology and research objectives	8
2.2 Theoretical framework	10
2.2.1 Social Constructivism	11
2.2.2 Framing theory	11
3. LITERATURE REVIEW	14
3.1 Framing in favor of same-sex marriage	15
3.1.1 Civil rights / human rights	15
3.1.2 Equality	15
3.1.3. Discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens	16
3.1.4. Separation of Church and state	17
3.1.5 Not a threat	17
3.1.6 Protection of the children	17
3.1.7 Expansion of conservative ideals.....	18
3.2 Framing against same-sex marriage	19
3.2.1 Protection of children	19
3.2.2 Lawlessness	20
3.2.3 Slippery slope	20
3.2.4 Religion	20
3.2.5 One man and one woman / history of marriage.....	21
3.2.6 Reproduction as a core of marriage.....	22
3.2.7 Lack of public support.....	23
4. CZECH AND GERMAN CHRISTIAN DEMOCRATIC MPS' DISCOURSE	24
4.1 Frames used against same-sex marriage:	25
4.1.1 Protection of children	25
4.1.2 Lawlessness	27
4.1.3 Slippery slope	29
4.1.4 Religion	31
4.1.5 One man and one woman / history of marriage.....	33

4.1.6	Reproduction as a core of marriage	36
4.1.7	Lack of public support	37
4.2	New frames used against same-sex marriage	38
4.2.1	There is no right for marriage and no right for a child	38
4.2.2	Equality without marriage	39
4.2.3	The third way	41
4.3	Frames used in favor of same-sex marriage	42
4.3.1	Civil rights / human rights	43
4.3.2	Equality	43
4.3.3	Discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens	44
4.3.4	Separation of Church and state	45
4.3.5	Not a threat	46
4.3.6	Protection of children/children's well-being.....	46
4.3.7	Expansion of conservative ideals.....	47
4.4	New frames used in favor of same-sex marriage	48
4.4.1	Public support	48
4.4.2	Reproduction is not the core of marriage	49
4.4.3	Does not go against the Basic Law	49
4.4.4	Meaning of marriage changes.....	50
CONCLUSION	52
BIBLIOGRAPHY	55
ANNEXES	66
Personal statements and sources directly from the MPs	66
Jürgen Klimke (CDU, Hamburg)	66
Heribert Hirte (CDU, Cologne II.)	69
Peter Tauber (CDU, Main-Kinzig-Wetterau, Schotten)	70
Christoph Bergner (CDU, Halle)	70
ABSTRACT	72

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - Party positions on same-sex marriage in Czechia.....	6
Table 2 - Party positions on same-sex marriage in Germany	7

INTRODUCTION

The debate about allowing same-sex couples to get married and to receive the same rights as opposite-sex couples has been around in the world for a while. This paper focuses on the Christian Democratic parties' discourse in 2 countries, Czechia and Germany, since there are certain differences in approaches to this question between these countries and parties, although they are neighbors. While in Germany the struggle for same-sex marriage ended in 2017, when the Parliament voted overwhelmingly in favor of same-sex marriage, in the Czech Republic, the debate is still ongoing, although (as of May 2024), there have been certain improvements in the partnership status for same-sex couples.

It is natural that when it comes to same-sex couples, there are wishes for equal legal protection of their relationship and mainly legal protections for the children that are brought up in the so-called rainbow families. At the beginning of the new millennium, there used to be mainly calls for a sort of weaker form of protection, registered partnerships (or similar unions with a different name), and as time progressed, the discourse has shifted more towards demands for full Marriage equality, mainly in the Western world, with some exceptions such as Taiwan, Slovenia, and others (Euronews and AFP 2022).

As already mentioned, while Germany has already legalized same-sex marriage, its neighboring country to the east, Czechia, has not yet, despite the long ongoing debates in the Parliament. It is interesting to observe this phenomenon. The most interesting thing about it is the different role that the Christian Democratic parties in both countries played when debating about the bill. We can ask the question why has Germany, predominantly a Christian country legalized same-sex marriage, while Czechia, mainly an atheist country, has not yet? In Germany the law had passed while in the German parliament (Bundestag), the biggest party, and the governing party, was the German Christian Democratic party (CDU/CSU). Currently, as of the year 2024, there are Christian Democrats (KDU-ČSL) in the Czech government as well, but same-sex marriage seems to be unacceptable to them. So naturally the questions that come to one's mind are "Has the German CDU/CSU done something differently from the Czech KDU-ČSL?" One's mind would also go into the question if religiosity even plays a role in the reason why some countries reject same-sex marriage. But if so, why did some German Christian Democrats vote in favor of it? And if not, why are (presumably) all Czech Christian Democrats strictly against?

The existing research on the differences regarding positions on same-sex marriage in Christian Democratic parties is somewhat limited. Some papers examine the discourse, such as in the Czech case, Čižmářová (2023) conducted a framing analysis that examined the discourse about civil unions in the Czech Parliament between 2013 and 2017. Fiala (2023) also discussed same-sex unions in the Czech political discourse and Pavlovský (2018) examined how the campaign for marriage equality was presented in the media until 2018. In the German case, there is more specific research done about the topic, including analyses that show the different stances towards same-sex marriage within the Christian Democratic party in the 2013, 2017 and 2021 elections (Jankowski 2022). Another one is, for instance, a paper that examines the voting behavior of Christian Democratic voters regarding rewarding the candidates who voted in favor of same-sex marriage, rather than those who voted against it (Kauder and Potrafke 2018, Kauder and Potrafke 2021). Media analysis was also done by for instance Kania (2019). But no comparative analyses which would compare Czechia and Germany in this sense.

I believe this paper will be able to provide additional research even to the Czech literature, and it will open up the topic to a broader range of people while aiming to show the differences in the German and Czech discourse regarding legalizing (or not legalizing) of same-sex marriage, and answering my main research questions about *“Whether the political discourse of the German Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU) regarding same-sex marriage differs somehow from their affiliate Czech Christian Democratic party (KDU-ČSL)?”* Meaning if or how differently it is framed and presented to the public. And the second research question is *“Considering the fact that quite a few CDU/CSU MPs voted in favor of same-sex marriage (Ehe für Alle), while KDU-ČSL MPs are against, what are the reasons behind this difference of opinions?”* The paper will be held as a comparative discourse analysis for Germany and Czechia and will be using the framing theory to sort out the different argument patterns from the Christian Democratic parties.

As for the structure of this paper, before I look further into the discourse, I believe it is important to introduce the meaning of certain terms connected to this topic, including a brief mention of the differences between registered partnerships and marriages. Then a literature review will be conducted, that will examine the existing frames in the general discourse about the topic in the outside world, which will serve as an indicator for further research in my empirical part. Apart from examining the discourse in the Lower Houses of the Parliaments in Czechia and Germany, there will also be a few interesting remarks from some members of Parliament (MPs) in Germany, who I was able to get in touch with, and

their personal inputs will be able to open up the topic to us even more. These will be integrated into their corresponding frame, and the full text will be at the end of the paper in the Annexes.

1. TERMINOLOGY AND PARTY SUPPORT

1.1 *Same-sex marriage*

By same-sex marriage, we understand providing the same legal framework for homosexual couples to enter the institution of marriage, with the same rights and obligations as for heterosexual couples. Another term that could be used in this paper is “marriage equality” or “gay marriage.” What is worth noting is that by the term “marriage equality” I do not mean having 2 separate institutions (such as marriage for heterosexual couples, and partnership for homosexual couples), despite them in some proposals having the same rights and obligations (even including joint adoption). But for the simplicity of this paper, I will not address them as equal institutions.

1.2 *Registered partnership*

Registered partnership often in many countries tends to be the step between “no rights” and “full rights” for same-sex couples. In Czechia, the bill about registered partnerships came into force in 2006 after several discussions and even the Presidential veto (that was overridden by the Parliament) (ČTK 2016). In 2024, the Czech Parliament came up with several amendments to the current legal framework, and this gave more rights to same-sex couples (such as the ability to have common marital property, joint tenancy, or widow’s pension), and even changed the name from registered partnership to simply *partnership* (ČTK 2024). Although this does improve the situation, it does not consider the situation regarding children much. That is one of the biggest differences between marriage and partnerships. Interesting to point out is that this was an amendment proposal to the full marriage equality proposal, and it was proposed by a Christian Democratic MP Jiří Navrátil (ČTK 2024). Before this step, the differences between the registered partnership and marriage were more significant.

In Germany on the other hand, registered partnerships became legal in 2001 until the full marriage equality bill passed in 2017 (Lebenspartnerschaft.de n.d.). That brings us to the situation today, where German same-sex couples are able to enjoy more rights than Czech same-sex couples, despite the countries being neighbors and the distance between these couples can be even in just a few kilometers in distance. If to follow the trend set by the Germans, Czechia should have accepted same-sex marriage in 2022, considering the 5-year gap between the legalizations of registered partnerships.

1.3 LGBTQ

Under the abbreviation LGBTQ, other times used as LGBT and LGBTQ+, we understand people that do not fit the heteronormative role in the society. By this I mean people with a non-heterosexual orientation such as gays, lesbians, bisexuals, people who do not want to label themselves or are unsure (“queer”), or transgender people.

1.4 Parties and their stance on same-sex marriage

Before analyzing and further content, it is important to show the overall partisan support for same-sex marriage in each country. In Czechia, even if all Christian Democrats voted in favor of this proposal, it would still not have been enough for it to pass smoothly through the Parliament. The same is also true when it comes to the German case but considering the fact that all other parties voted in favor, the Christian Democratic votes were not necessary to approve it in the first place. Although, if the party opinion in Germany was as fragmented as in Czechia, the situation could have been different, due to the extensive amount of Christian Democratic MPs in the German Parliament. To demonstrate the percentage of the Christian Democratic parties in each Parliament, in Czechia KDU-ČSL 11.5 % of the MPs in the Chamber of Deputies, while currently being the 4th biggest party. On the other hand, in Germany, the percentage (before the bill was legalized) was significantly higher, being 37.89 %, making CDU/CSU the biggest group in the Bundestag. The overall party support of the Czech and German parties can be seen from this short overview.

1.4.1 Czechia

Since there has not been a vote on the actual proposal of same-sex marriage (instead, the MPs were voting about a different amendment), the party positions are quite difficult to state accurately. In order to show the party support according to my best abilities, I took into consideration the vote on the amendment, but also the long-term party behavior.

POLITICAL PARTY (BASED ON THE POSITION ON SAME-SEX MARRIAGE NUMBER OF MPS AS OF 2024) (AS OF 2024)

ANO 2011	✓/✗ (does not have a unanimous position about this proposal, therefore it is upon each MPs conscience)
ODS	✓/✗ (does not have a unanimous position either, leaning more towards being against same-sex marriage)
STAN	✓/✗ (mainly in favor of same-sex marriage, but in their manifesto from the joint ballot list with Piráti in 2021, they reserved a vote of conscience for each MP (Machová 2021))
KDU-ČSL (CHRISTIAN DEMOCRATIC PARTY)	✗ (against same-sex marriage)
SPD	✗ (unanimously against)
TOP 09	✓/✗ (according to the leader of the party, Markéta Pekarová Adamová, the party supports marriage equality (Pekarová Adamová 2024), however there are some conservative MPs in this party who are against same-sex marriage)
PIRÁTI	✓ (unanimously in favor of same-sex marriage)

Table 1 - Party positions on same-sex marriage in Czechia

Sources - Machová, Martina. 2021. "Jednota Nové Koalice Pirátů a STAN Má Svou Mez: Manželství pro Všechny." Seznam Zprávy. January 16, 2021. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.seznamzpravy.cz/clanek/jednota-nove-koalice-piratu-a-stan-ma-svou-mez-manzelstvi-pro-vsechny-137301>.

Pekarová Adamová, Markéta (@market_a). 2024. "Poslanecký klub @TOP09cz podpoří svými hlasy "manželství pro všechny". Je nejvyšší čas, aby se srovnala práva. Zároveň moc prosím, aby se debata vedla kultivovaně a nestala se nástrojem vyvolávání strachu a nenávisti. Častokrát jsme byli na plénu sněmovny svědky zraňujících slov. Nedopustme to. Twitter; February 6, 2024, 12:24PM. Accessed May 10, 2024. https://x.com/market_a/status/1754828404359340114.

1.4.2 Germany

In Germany, it is easier to describe since the parties already voted on the bill about same-sex marriage. Compared to the situation in Czechia, where due to political strategies, the MPs did not vote on the bill about same-sex marriage, but rather on the individual amendments (from the one with the least number of rights to the one with the most, while still called “partnership”). And the vote in the German Bundestag in 2017 shows us this:

POLITICAL PARTY (BASED ON THE NUMBER OF MPS 2013-2017)	POSITION ON SAME-SEX MARRIAGE (AS OF THE DAY OF THE VOTE IN 2017)
CDU/CSU (CHRISTIAN DEMOCRATIC PARTIES)	✔/✘ (75 out of 309 MPs voted in favor (Deutsches Bundestag 2017))
SPD	✔ (unanimously voted in favor of same-sex marriage)
DIE GRÜNEN	✔ (unanimously voted in favor of same-sex marriage)
FDP	✔ (unanimously voted in favor of same-sex marriage)
DIE LINKE	✔ (unanimously voted in favor of same-sex marriage)

Table 2 - Party positions on same-sex marriage in Germany

Source - Deutsches Bundestag, 2017. “Deutscher Bundestag - Namentliche Abstimmungen.” Deutscher Bundestag. July 30, 2017. <https://www.bundestag.de/parlament/plenum/abstimmung/abstimmung/?id=486>.

* Nowadays there is another party in the Bundestag, the AfD, which is a right-wing to far-right party which opposes same-sex marriage, but for this paper they are irrelevant (though they are gaining popular support in Germany, as of 2024), since they did not get to vote on this matter.

2. METHODOLOGY, RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Methodology and research objectives

Having explained the general background about the situation regarding same-sex marriage in both countries, I am moving to the next part of the paper, where the research objectives of the paper are mentioned, along with the methodology.

The **purpose** of this paper is to take a closer look and examine the different approaches to same-sex marriage in Germany and Czechia. To be more exact, to compare the different approaches by the Christian Democratic parties in both countries. Among some of the many arguments that parties often use against same-sex marriage is religion, which is why it is more than interesting to see the different outlooks from CDU/CSU and KDU-ČSL, both being parties with predominantly Christian values in their cores.

This paper was held as a **comparative discourse analysis using the framing theory** (which is connected to the social constructivist IR school) because the main thing that I am examining is the way these parties are talking about same-sex marriage and therefore how are they framing and shaping the discussion (framing theory is mentioned in the *theoretical framework* section). I am convinced that the way politicians (in this case Christian Democrats) are talking about a specific topic, can strongly influence the general mood in the public and their feelings towards any given topic. In this case, the topic is same-sex marriage. As an example, if a large number of politicians in high powers decide to frame the discourse of same-sex marriage as “*giving equal rights and duties to all citizens,*” the general mood will likely look at this topic from this side. But if they decide to label LGBTQ people as “*the others,*” and how “*the status quo is in danger,*” the majority of the population will likely feel threatened and therefore have more negative feelings towards this topic. On the other hand, I also believe that personal communication between people can play a role in shaping the politicians’ opinion, and therefore the opinion of the population (connected to social constructivism, which will be also elaborated in my *theoretical framework* part). If the citizens clearly show that they are in favor of same-sex marriage, the chances of the elected politicians to vote in favor are naturally higher, because they do not want to lose their position. The same applies if the population shows their disagreement with same-sex marriage. Therefore, the

relationship between the population and the politicians is interconnected and can affect each other from both top-down but also bottom-up.

Regarding the data that I will be using in this paper, the statements from the Christian Democratic members in the Lower House of the Parliaments (MPs) are the main sources of primary data that are used for the analysis. In those statements, I am looking at the different frames being used. To quickly mention the time limitations of this paper regarding this type of primary data, I decided to consider only the statements from the Czech Chamber of Deputies in the current cycle from 2021 until 2024 (the year of writing this paper), since same-sex marriage was heavily debated in this time period. As far as Germany is concerned, the statements are from the debates in the Bundestag before the legalization, which is the 2013-2017 period. Among the other sources of primary data are blogs and websites of the individual MPs (that are explaining their position and the way they frame their argument), or for instance newspaper interviews. About other primary sources, I have also reached out to all CDU/CSU MPs who served in the 2013-2017 German Bundestag and asked them if they could explain their reasoning for the way they voted. I was curious to see why German Christian Democrats sometimes voted in favor, but the Czech Christian Democrats did not. With one of the MPs who I contacted, I managed to conduct a short interview that was able to help me understand this topic more and provide interesting insights, to dive deeper.

Regarding secondary sources of data, they were used for my theoretical part, where I was able to identify the individual frames that exist in the literature from other countries. To research this, I looked for journal articles, books, and websites, mainly coming from Google Scholar, that were discussing *framing theory* and *frames* regarding same-sex marriage, or specifically *framing of same-sex marriage debates* during the legalization attempts. The data used in this paper are mostly qualitative, focusing on the speeches and the discourse, rather than statistics. Numbers are still used in this work, but not in such an extent to be of a quantitative nature.

Going back to the personal contacting of the German Christian Democratic MPs, I contacted them via email and Messenger with some overall questions, to which I received 6 responses. The rest did not react to my email/private message. Several email addresses were already deactivated, most likely meaning that these MPs are no longer active in politics. Out of those who responded, 3 of them voted in favor of the proposal, and 3 voted against.

Among those who answered, apart from the MP with whom I managed to conduct an interview, another MP provided me with a link to his blog, where he explains why he believes it is important to allow same-sex couples to be able to marry, along with his personal reasoning for voting in favor. The MP who voted against explained to me why he believes it was a wrong decision to legalize it in the first place. These primary sources are significantly important if we want to understand the personal reasonings of the way a certain MP voted and the way they frame their position, which has an impact on the general discourse too. In the personal interview, I was able to ask him questions that I based on the theory that was chosen for this paper, which is *framing theory*, that will later be explained. The full list of the questions is at the end of this Bachelor paper, in the Annexes.

My contribution to the existing knowledge would be not only by the personal interview with the MP and the responses I received but also in the way that although there had already been certain papers regarding discourse about same-sex marriage in both countries, this paper aims to show the contrast and differences, mainly between the Christian Democratic parties. The name “Christian Democratic” would suggest that they should be similar, given the fact that both have roots in Christianity, but even with that, there are certain differences between the parties and the way they look at specific proposals (in this case it is same-sex marriage) or the society itself.

The **research questions** I am looking at in this paper are:

1. Does the political discourse of the German Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU) regarding same-sex marriage differ somehow from their affiliate Czech Christian Democratic party (KDU-ČSL)?
2. Considering the fact that quite a few CDU/CSU MPs voted in favor of same-sex marriage (Ehe für Alle), while KDU-ČSL MPs are against it, what are the reasons behind this difference of opinions?

2.2 Theoretical framework

After explaining the research objectives and the methodology of this paper, I am moving on to guide you through the theory that I chose to be able to analyze the given content. As the theory, I chose the **framing theory**. This theory is connected to the **social constructivist IR school**. As far as other researchers and their choices of theories, Kristýna Čižmářová (2023) chose to connect constructivism and framing

analysis in her paper as well, therefore even previous research suggests that this combination is credible and can bring value and sense to the topic.

2.2.1 Social Constructivism

As I will later mention in the explanation of framing theory, to shortly mention it here, the general discourse (and therefore the general attitude) can be shaped thanks to the way the people in power choose to frame their arguments. Which is closely connected to social constructivism, to which Lev Vygotsky (who is one of the most important people in social constructivism) in his works says “*that the process of knowing is affected by other people and is mediated by community and culture*” (Amineh and Asl 2015, p.10), as well as through the choice of language (Amineh and Asl 2015). André Kukla adds that reality is socially constructed, meaning that our human interactions create our reality (Kukla 2000, as cited in Kim 2001).

In this paper, language is important, because the words the MPs decide to choose show us how they are framing their position on the matter. Vivien Burr further explains social constructivism in the way that there is no knowledge and reality in advance, but they come from interactions of people between each other, therefore there are no *facts* (Burr 2015). Beaumie Kim tells us, how social constructivism depends on interpretations of *reality* (does not exist according to social constructivists, but is created through interactions), *knowledge* (is created by human interactions as well, taking into consideration culture), and *learning* (human interactions make learning possible) (Kim 2001, as cited in Amineh and Asl 2015). Last but not least, regarding social constructivism and its beliefs, Cornelia Ulbert in her work says that the “*social world, as accessible to us, is constructed through the way in which we deal with others, the ideas we share about the world and how we experience our environment*” (Ulbert 2014, p.248).

2.2.2 Framing theory

Regarding *framing theory*, framing originally comes from Erving Goffman, who explains it as something we use to understand and organize situations in our daily lives (Goffman 1974, as mentioned in McFarland 2011). But as Miriam Smith suggests, some scholars see framing as something that people use to get their view out there in the political field (Smith 2007). By framing an argument in a certain way, we are letting others know “*what that situation is about*” (Perrin 2006, as cited in McFarland 2011, p.258), and therefore we’re giving an example of how we see it and how we want to lead the debate. A

really good way to show the power of framing is mentioned in a paper by Pizmony-Levy and Ponce (2013) with the example of unemployment. Presenting it as a 95 % worth of employment sounds way better and more convincing than if you tell the public there is a 5 % of unemployment in the country. Despite both being the same information but just framed differently, leading to a different perception of the problem (Pizmony-Levy and Ponce 2013). David Snow and Robert D Benford explain framing as simplifying the world while paying attention only to for example specific circumstances or objects, based on your experience (Snow and Benford 1992, as cited in Ghoshal 2009). A very interesting explanation of framing is explained by Nelson and Kinder who say that “*frames ... provide a mental recipe for preparing an opinion about an issue*” (Nelson and Kinder 1996, p.1058, as quoted in Gainous 2016, p.5). According to Paul M. Sniderman and Sean M. Theriault, the way we frame an argument can significantly influence others’ opinions (Sniderman and Theriault 2004, as cited in McFarland 2011). However, connected to the debate about same-sex marriage, Pizmony-Levy and Ponce disagree and say that it does not really matter how you frame it, since it does not significantly change the general public opinion (Pizmony-Levy and Ponce 2013). I, on the other hand, believe it does play a significant role in the public perception. This could be true perhaps for people with a set opinion from the beginning, but for people who are unsure or are willing to listen to both sides, the way we frame it can influence them.

I believe *framing theory* suits this format of my Bachelor thesis the most because based on the data that I will collect from the speeches in the National Parliaments and other sources of data I mentioned above, I will be sorting the results into individual groups of arguments, so-called *frames*, which will be able to visualize the main areas of arguments when talking about same-sex marriage. To provide a short example to clearly explain how I will be working with the frames, let’s take the general frame *welfare of children*. One framing of the argument (still within this frame) would be that by allowing same-sex couples, the child would have a disadvantage over other children, because they would not have the standard model of a family, being one man and one woman, to provide the child with both of a masculine and feminine role model. A contrary framing to this would be that by allowing same-sex couples to get married, we are in fact improving the stability of their family, in terms of the legal part, where now the parents would have full parental rights over the child, and the child could be raised in a more secure environment than before.

The way I am using the framing theory in this comparative paper is that after conducting the literature review, where I get a rough idea of what possible frames we can expect in the debate, in the empirical part I will sort out the frames based on the statements from each country, and the frames will be used for

a comparison, to demonstrate how or if the framing differs in one country from another. This theory makes sense to be used since often the general discourse (and therefore the general attitude) is shaped thanks to the way the people in power choose to frame their arguments.

On the other hand, I am aware that choosing this theory has its limitations. For instance, it will not be able to fully explain why the result of legalization was different in each country. Or that my paper will not be able to cover all of the possible frames that these parties are using in all existing statements or identify them in a way that another researcher would. The main focus is on the comparison of the statements (sorted out into frames) between the 2 countries.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Now I am moving to the part, where I will be listing the possible frames that exist around the topic of same-sex marriage. As I mentioned in the methodological part, for researching this, I was looking at journal articles, books and websites discussing *framing theory*, *frames* about same-sex marriage or partnerships, and preferably already *framing of same-sex marriage debates* during the legalization attempts.

A lot of this gathered data is from the early to late 2000s but listening to the discourse even nowadays (it being 2024), we can see that the majority of the occurring frames are still relevant in the discussions, both those in favor and against the proposal. These frames that were found in this part come from all different parts of society, not only from Christian Democratic parties. These frames will serve as a guide for the empirical part of this Bachelor paper, where I will be comparing the two countries. An important note to say is that not all possible frames of the arguments are mentioned in the review, therefore new or slightly different frames can come up in the process of the analysis in the empirical part of this paper.

Regarding the preliminary results of the literature review, when it comes to the most widely used frames in opposition to same-sex marriage in the discourses around the world, are the *protection of children*, *lawlessness*, *slippery slope*, *religion*, *one man and one woman / history*, *reproduction as the core of marriage* and *lack of public support*. On the other hand, talking about the most frequently used frames in favor of same-sex marriage around the world, we can mention *civil / human rights*, *equality*, *discrimination / tolerance / respect*, *separation of Church and state*, *not a threat*, *protection of children*, *expansion of conservative ideals*. Although there are surely more frames, these seem to be some of the most frequent ones, and it deserves to be mentioned in this paper how they are used.

Having briefly mentioned the general findings from the literature review, I will now individually talk about the possible frames that I found when conducting my research more in detail. I will be mentioning the area of the frame, and for each, I will explain how it is talked about.

3.1 Framing in favor of same-sex marriage

3.1.1 Civil rights / human rights

This, alongside the frame of equality, seems to be one of the most prominent frames. Supporters of this frame are framing their position in the way, that in the status quo (meaning before legalization happens), marriage is exclusively opened only to heterosexual people. It is known that marriage provides stability and benefits for families. This leaves same-sex couples outside of this possibility, leaving them with worsened conditions for their families. That is when the civil rights framing of the issue steps in, in order to open up marriage even to same-sex couples. Sometimes, when the Constitutional ban on same-sex marriage is at stake, supporters of same-sex marriage frame it in the way that if it goes through, it can be seen as a precedent for other groups of citizens being excluded from other rights in the future, as for instance, Hull (2001) talks about it. To show the intensity of the use of this frame, in an analysis done by Warren and Bloch framing in terms of civil rights / human rights was the most used, when analyzing newspaper discourse (Warren and Bloch 2014, as cited in Colistra and Johnson 2019).

3.1.2 Equality

For many supporters of same-sex marriage, the inability to get married represents a form of inequality. Because opposite-sex couples can get married and gain all the benefits of the institution, but if a same-sex couple wants to get married, it does not work like that. Or at best, they are able to enter the (registered) partnership, which in many countries does not provide the same rights and duties as marriage does. Therefore, the framers of this argument focus on the fact that gay couples do not want to be superior to anyone (and have more rights or special rights), but instead the same rights as straight couples already have (Hull 2001). In Czechia, a way of framing that is widely used within this frame is “*láska je jen jedna*” (“*there’s just one form of love*”) (Jílková 2023), very often used by the supporters to pinpoint the validity and equality of same-sex relationships in connection to opposite-sex relationships.

This frame is also often connected to the Constitution framing. In the Constitution of a country, it usually guarantees the same treatment for all and same rights (Hull 2001). This is exactly what the supporters of the equality framing point at, that this section of the Constitution is not fully used, at least not in the desired way. As one of the influential framers of the equality but also Constitution frame, Barack Obama can be mentioned when he said “*Our nation was founded on a bedrock principle that we are all created*

equal ... the Supreme Court recognized that the Constitution guarantees marriage equality. In doing so, they've reaffirmed that all Americans are entitled the equal protection of the law. That all people should be treated equally, regardless of who they are or who they love" (Obama 2015, as quoted in Grube and van Acker 2016). Dennis Grube and Elizabeth van Acker refer to it that Obama was able to show the principal values of the American nation and also showed a reason why he believes it was in the interest of the nation (Grube and van Acker 2016). About the frequency of use of this frame, McFarland (2011) shows that equality was the most used frame in her research.

Tyler Johnson talks about the fact that when a person frames same-sex marriage in the frame of rights, justice, or fairness (all this falling under equality), the chances of the recipients of this message to be against same-sex marriage decrease (Johnson 2012). But on the other hand, if the framer who is in against same-sex marriage decides to frame the argument within *morality*, the chances of opposition to same-sex marriage increase (Johnson 2012). From looking at the keywords in Johnson's paper on page 1075, we can tell that the morality framing is very often linked to the religious frame, meanwhile the equality frame is connected with words such as already mentioned fairness, rights, justice, or liberties, independence or freedom.

3.1.3. Discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens

This frame is often used to demonstrate the need to stand up and combat oppression since hatred plays a role in the world and there is a need for tolerance in our society (Hull 2001). And according to this frame, it should be done exactly by legalizing same-sex marriage, which will be THE one, or at least one of the steps that will promote a more tolerant society where diversity is not looked down on, but instead valued and respected. Hull compares the fact that same-sex couples can't enter marriage to other forms of oppression (Hull 2001), and McFarland adds that not allowing these couples to be married "*unfairly punishes gays*" (McFarland 2011, p.265). Connected to the frame of tolerance and respect is also *love*. Hatalsky and Trumble show us that sometimes when the argument is framed as *love*, it tends to be more persuasive than if sticking to the previous *rights* framing (Hatalsky and Trumble 2012, as cited in Adam and Cooper 2017).

Connected to this, we can mention the argument of *discrimination of a certain group*. Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper (2009) suggest that in their research, discrimination was the most frequent frame on the

supporting side. On the other hand, the notion of “one man and one woman” being the core of marriage proved to be the most widely used one with the opponents, in the same research.

3.1.4. Separation of Church and state

Nowadays, many countries are stepping onto the path where they are limiting the amount to which the Church has influence on what is happening in the national politics and as to what laws should go through and which ones should be prevented. This is especially true in countries with a low share of religious population. Raj Ghoshal suggests that marriage does not have to represent a religious institution for all people, but for some, it means mostly mutual agreement within the couple to stick by each other and care about each other (Ghoshal 2009). With the separation of Church and state, it gives people the decision to choose which institution to join, whether the religious marriage or the civil marriage. Therefore, according to the supporters of this frame, they frame their argument in the way that the Church should not prevent same-sex couples from getting married, due to the separation of Church and state. Although, this frame is more sensitive and personal because it talks about one’s faith.

3.1.5 Not a threat

Same-sex marriage not being a threat to anyone, and not negatively affecting anyone (McFarland 2011), is a pretty common frame. You can especially hear it from the Czech politicians who support marriage equality. They often say that “*Manželství pro všechny (Marriage for all) will not hurt anyone, but it will help many people.*” Although this is a sensible framing of an argument, it feels like sort of an empty argument, although it focuses on individual liberties. There is not much value in it, which would move people and motivate them to stand either on the supporting or opposing side of the proposal.

3.1.6 Protection of the children

Although this frame is mainly heard on the side of the opponents of same-sex marriage, it is not non-existent on the supporting side either. This framing of the argument is able to provide proof that allowing same-sex couples to get married and be able to get all the benefits (as mentioned already above), will significantly improve the legal (but not only legal) stability of the children growing up in the so-called rainbow families (where the parents are of the same sex). Even if same-sex marriage is not legal, individual persons can adopt, and therefore kids already do grow up in these families. So, the argument is not about preventing LGBTQ couples from raising children (because that is not even the question),

but rather the focus should be on how to make the life of the kids easier, so that if unfortunately, something happens to one of the caregivers, that the other one can claim parental rights and continue taking care of the child, which is what this frame is exactly taking into consideration. This sounds like an influential way of framing. Despite this being an important issue, it is not as much talked about.

As Katherine McFarland talks about it, the supporters of the “protection of children” frame say it is a pro-family thing to do and it serves as protection for the kids who grow up in rainbow families (McFarland 2011). Within this frame is another sub-frame, that you can notice not only in the Czech discourse, saying that if we legalize same-sex marriage, it will lead to improved mental health and a lower suicide rate among children who are accepting their sexuality. Even for instance, Egale (2001, as cited in Smith 2007) shows that. The reasoning for this is that the legalization of same-sex marriage, and therefore making their relationships equal to the opposite-sex couples, on the legal level, will send a signal to people that they are equal. This frame, when expanded, is a very strong frame, focusing on the lives and feelings of our society’s children, therefore it can be effective in the legalization process when explained properly.

3.1.7 Expansion of conservative ideals

This is sort of a different take on the argument in favor of same-sex marriage. This frame was most famously used by the then British Prime Minister David Cameron, under whose Cabinet same-sex marriage was introduced. David Cameron was a politician in the British Conservative Party, but that did not phase an obstacle for him to become a supporter of the proposal. He took the conservative values on which his party stands and framed them according to his view of it. This take was a very strong and successful one. What he did was he framed it as equality, but also he saw allowing same-sex couples to get married “*as a natural extension of a conservative ideology that recognized the power of marriage to hold society together*” (Grube and van Acker 2016, p.7-8). According to him, it was “*also about ... commitment, Conservatives believe in the ties that bind us; that society is stronger when we make vows to each other and support each other. So I don’t support gay marriage despite being a Conservative. I support gay marriage because I’m a Conservative*” (Cameron 2011, as quoted in Grube and van Acker 2016, p.7). Coming from a PM of a country, this framing can significantly change the trajectory of the opinions on this issue within the whole political field. More Conservatives now “can” support same-sex marriage, because that position is now “validated” by a high-position Conservative. David Cameron also

followed up on his argument by using the *protection children* frame in favor, where he mentions *stability* that would be gained from the legalization (Grube and van Acker 2016).

3.2 Framing against same-sex marriage

3.2.1 Protection of children

This frame has two sides to it. One was described above in the support section, but this second one is more common in the general discourse revolving around same-sex marriage. From the Czech discourse over the time, one of the altogether main arguments is the protection of children. The right of the child to know its birth parents, and implying the importance of the traditional family, that is one man and one woman, is a common framing. Christopher Fritzsche and Juliane Lang explain that the core argument is that if a child does not have one mom and one dad who are raising the child and are acting according to their gender roles, the idea of a problem-free childhood goes away and instead identity problems and psychological problems can arise (Fritzsche and Lang 2019). Often you can also hear the argument that if a child would have two moms or two dads, the child could become sort of an outcast in school or other environments. Though there could be debates whether it occurs due to the fact that the child has 2 moms or dads, or because of the lack of tolerance and acceptance, connecting this frame to the *tolerance* frame above in the previous section.

An argument that Bob Egelko talks about using this frame is that when we allow only one man and one woman to have a wedding, it will therefore “*promote responsible sex child rearing, and ultimately ensures the future of humanity*” (Egelko 2010, p.A1, as quoted in Warren and Bloch 2014). Some people within this frame go even further with the framing and say that if a child is raised by a same-sex couple, it could affect the child’s sexuality (Hall et al. 2019). On the other hand, there are also scholars who disagree with this claim.

Čižmářová (2023) found out in her research that often in the Czech discourse, regarding the topic of children, politicians frame it in the way that there is no *right* to have a child. And based on this argument, politicians frame their opposition towards same-sex marriage and adoption.

3.2.2 Lawlessness

For many, this frame is connected to the *Constitution* (Hull 2001) and framing the opinion around it. The supporters of same-sex marriage can say that because the Constitution ensures all are equal and worthy of the same rights (no matter what sex we are). The opponents, on the other hand, would argue with upholding the current law (Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper 2009) and the protection of the Constitution and the prevention of unnecessary changes of it in order to expand marriage. Tony Abbott tried to frame the discourse in Australia primarily around the legal part. That means that he as a traditionalist, wants to protect the Constitution, not that he wants to be against or in favor of same-sex marriage (Abbott 2013 as cited in Grube and van Acker 2016). Some (more towards the extremes) frame their argument as that same-sex couples want to destroy values and marriage, and even compare them to terrorists (Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper 2009), but this view is not a prevalent one in the discourse.

3.2.3 Slippery slope

A framing that is often heard is that allowing same-sex marriage would lead to other things being legalized. Among some of those mentioned is usually polygamy, or somewhat “jokingly” that it would lead to the normalization of sex and marriage with animals, as both Hull (2001) and McFarland (2011) show in their works. Even the then Prime Minister of Australia, Tony Abbott, had someone resign over their statements in 2012 engaging in this framing of endorsement of bestiality as a result of opening marriage to same-sex couples (Cullen 2012). Interestingly enough, the person was in the Liberal Party, which you would expect to have a different stance.

3.2.4 Religion

I believe this is one of the most widely used frames in the discourse around the world. The opponents of same-sex marriage very often explain their position in regard to their religious beliefs, in which marriage is for one man and one woman. A very popular saying within the religious frame is “*Adam and Eve, not Adam and Steve*” (Hall et al. 2019). This is to demonstrate the Christian principle that in the beginning, it was one man and one woman. Some add on top that this position is not to mistreat or spread hate on LGBTQ people, but rather to protect God’s institution of marriage and do what is right (Hull 2001). On the other hand, there are Christian denominations around the world in those countries that legalized same-sex marriage, which do allow LGBTQ couples to join the religious institution of marriage. Very often

this frame is linked to the *morality* frame (Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper 2009), therefore emphasizing that same-sex partnerships inherently are less moral than opposite-sex partnerships. If a person attends Church, it often is more likely for them to be against same-sex marriage according to Sherkat et al. (2011, as cited in Colistra and Johnson 2019). Churches in countries are often in the position of a strong opposition player when the discussion about same-sex marriage happens.

And in countries with a lower separation of Church and state, the influence on the discourse but also the decision is more significant. In the UK after legalization, Churches argued that it could mean a weakening of the status of marriage and also it might hurt families, according to the findings of Grube and van Acker (2016). In the US, the religious frame is also pretty significant, because of the high share of the religious population. In Hall et al. (2019), their research shows that some people frame it as that “*allowing LGBTQ couples to marry infringes upon the religious rights of people whose religion specifically bans homosexuality*” (Hall et al. 2019, p.17). This though can be rebutted also in the religious frame, with the framing that religious freedom exists, therefore my religion should not dictate your religion and vice-versa.

3.2.5 One man and one woman / history of marriage

Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper (2009) mention in their research that the frame of *one woman and one man* was the most common on the opposition side. In general, people often explain the fact their opposition to same-sex marriage in the way that *marriage* as a word implies that it is a covenant between one woman and one man, therefore there is nothing like “same-sex marriage.” In Hull’s paper (2001) she mentions someone’s statement that the word is even *oxymoronic*. Even some MPs in Czechia were using that framing and adding that the problem for them with same-sex marriage is the *word*, not the *rights* (including adoption in most cases). Unfortunately, as the latest voting in Czechia suggests, it is not just about the word, despite the opposition to the proposal was very often framing their disapproval in that way.

Other people express their concerns more in the way that because of the *history* and the meaning of the word, marriage deserves proper *protection* (meaning codifying in the Law that it is only between one man and one woman). This would, according to them, ensure the protection of democracy and morality (Hull 2001). Even other scholars, such as McFarland (2011), agree that this frame is common. President George W. Bush expressed his support for this frame of *protection* in his speech, where he talked about

marriage between opposite-sex partners serving as a safety lock for the stability in society (Bush 2004, as quoted in McFarland 2011, p.263). Katherine Hull stated in her paper that when using the *protection of marriage* argument, it is more likely to persuade other people, than by framing it as *denying civil rights* (Hull 2001). The reason why this frame is connected to the one man and one woman / history frame is that the people who choose to frame their stance with the *protection* frame usually mention the history behind marriage, how it has always been one man and one woman (Hull 2001), despite other aspects changing over time. But this core definition has never changed, so it is an essential part of the definition (McFarland 2011). Therefore, it is not about discriminating against anyone, and it is not about civil rights (Hull 2001), but rather as preservation of values. While this argument certainly has validity, we can't forget that interracial marriage was a problem before in some countries as well (Hall et al. 2019), now no one would ever think twice about it.

One counterargument on the supporting side, regarding this frame of tradition, says that same-sex marriage was presented to the public as something that would throw away what the society has worked for in the past, being the preservation of traditions and traditional values (Hall et al. 2019).

3.2.6 Reproduction as a core of marriage

Another popular frame is *reproduction* as being one of the vital parts of the purpose of marriage, which will ensure the continuation of our society (Warren and Bloch 2014). Marriage is an institution through which couples are to bring children to the world. Framers of this argument believe that since same-sex couples can't conceive a child together, they should not be able to get married and claim the benefits. That is also examined in Fritzsche and Lang's (2019) paper, where they mention a saying by Manfred Spieker, a Christian conservative sociologist, who agreeingly said: "*The essential difference between same-sex partnerships and marriage is that the former lacks the potential for procreation and upbringing of offspring*" (Spieker 2015, as quoted in Fritzsche and Lang 2019, p.523). Critically evaluating this, when someone uses this framing as the primary one, it has certain gaps in it. As a society we allow opposite-sex partners to get married and we do not check whether they are planning on having children, as well as we allow infertile or elderly couples to get married.

3.2.7 Lack of public support

Back in the day, *lack of public support* was also one of the occurring frames in the debate (Zheng and Chan 2020). That meant that politicians should not vote in favor of same-sex marriage when it's not the will of the majority. Among some statements are for instance “*How can I respect anyone's wishes to marry, when they don't want to respect the voters ... and the very fibers of democracy*” (Olmsted 2008, as quoted in *SFGATE* 2008, as originally cited in Warren and Bloch 2014, p.510).

However, it is observable that the support is growing as time goes, and in both Czechia and Germany, the support before legalization was for the majority of the population, according to the polls (Centrum pro výzkum veřejného mínění, Sociologický ústav AV ČR, v. v. i., Kyselá, and Čadová 2023, p.3; Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes, Küpper, and Klocke 2017, p.3). This frame therefore has links to democracy and the protection of democracy, understood as the will of the people. Nowadays, we can tie it with democracy as well, but more so on the other side of the spectrum, being in favor of same-sex marriage.

4. CZECH AND GERMAN CHRISTIAN DEMOCRATIC MPS' DISCOURSE

In the previous part, I looked at the frames that exist in other papers, regarding discussions about same-sex marriage in the past. The results showed several frames in favor and against the proposal. Having explained what the individual frames talk about, now I am moving on to the actual comparative analysis part of my paper, where I will discuss the statements from Germany and Czechia and mention which frames were mentioned in their speeches from the Lower Chambers of the Parliaments. The objective of this chapter is to compare the frames and statements in Germany and Czechia and see where the opinions might be somehow different, despite them both being Christian Democratic parties. As I have already stated in the previous chapter, the list of frames in my literature review is not final. As time changes, the general opinion changes with it, and therefore there are newly emerged frames in the discourse that I have not mentioned yet. These will be mentioned below. For each of the frames, I will be looking both at Czechia and Germany and I will be comparing them.

A limitation of this research that comes to my mind is that it is likely that there are other frames or arguments that both Christian Democratic parties agree with, but they could have already been said during the parliamentary debates by members of another party, and not Christian Democrats themselves. Therefore, this research does not provide a full-on detailed explanation of why and how the stances on same-sex marriage differ, but instead, I am more focusing on the statements the Christian Democratic MPs have said themselves during the Parliamentary debates, which, of course, does not represent all their possible opinions. Meaning that in a way, this can show sort of a distorted image of the situation.

Because there was no Czech Christian Democratic MP that expressed their support for same-sex marriage, this part of the paper will start with the frames that are used in opposition to it. After mentioning those, I will describe the newly emerged frames against same-sex marriage both in Germany and Czechia, followed by a section focusing on the frames used in favor of the proposal, and the newly emerged frames for that part as well. The data that I was able to get from my personal communications with the MPs will be integrated into the frames when discussing how the discourse looked like. The full interview and insights from the communication will be at the end of the paper, in the Annexes.

Another point worth mentioning, before going any further, is that despite the heavy opposition to same-sex marriage from the Christian Democratic MPs, no mentions of the unnaturalness of homosexuality, or immorality, were mentioned.

Surprisingly to me, a lot of times, the argumentation of the MPs (both in Czech and German cases) was not clearly framed in one specific way. Very often the frames were intertwining with each other, for instance, the *history* frame was interconnected with the *religious* frame or other frames. Therefore, this *sorting out* into these frames certainly has its limitations and other researchers might connect the individual statements to other frames than in this paper, however, based on the frames I identified in the literature review, sorting them out in this way made sense.

4.1 Frames used **against** same-sex marriage:

4.1.1 Protection of children

Protection of children (including children's rights), for example the right of a child to know its birth parents was the most commonly occurring framing of disapproval of same-sex marriage in the Czech Christian Democratic discourse, during the debates in the Chamber of Deputies between 2021-2024. More accurately, the debate was ongoing during 2023 and 2024, when it came to an end with a compromise amendment (proposed by the Christian Democratic KDU-ČSL), that did not include neither the adoption rights nor the name "marriage." Instead, the MPs found common ground on renaming registered partnerships to simply partnerships. While in the Czech discourse, the child's right to *know* its parents was the most widely used frame, in the German discourse, although the *children protection* frame was important, it was not the most used one.

Among the Czech framers of the right to *know* its parents is for instance MP Aleš Dufek, who says that the child should be able to be aware of its biological parents and overall, its origin (Dufek 2023, May 31). MP Hayato Okamura and MP Pavla Golasowská are mentioning more or less the same argument, about knowing the parents. To the previous statement MP Dufek adds rather ironically that he doesn't "*know if there are any new findings in biology that a person can arise from two sperm cells or, possibly, from two eggs*" (Dufek 2023, May 31).

Some Czech MPs, such as Romana Bělohávková, clearly expressed that they see children's rights as the top priority in this matter (Bělohávková 2023, June 1). With this overall frame, there had been multiple

arguments connected to it. Such as the need for a masculine and feminine role in the child's life, as the healthiest form of growing up, which has been mentioned numerous times as well. Framers of this argument are explaining the opposition to the proposal in the way that they can't allow same-sex marriage (which includes adoption rights), because it means the child will not have the most natural environment for growing up, a mother and a father.

"However, we know that children learn by imitation and that they need models of motherhood and fatherhood for their healthy, harmonious development. I am not saying that this model must always be the biological parent, but the model of masculinity and femininity is truly irreplaceable for children." – **Romana Bělohávková** (June 1, 2023)

According to MP Romana Bělohávková, growing up in a rainbow family is not ideal, connecting again to the need for a feminine and masculine role for proper development. This relates back to the claim that Fritzsche and Lang (2019) used in their paper, regarding the possibilities of identity problems. However, she does admit in the same statement, that she is aware that there are happy rainbow families (Bělohávková 2023, June 2). Later in her statement, she mentions the lack of studies on child development in rainbow families and expresses her worry about the credibility of existing studies (Bělohávková 2023, June 1). In response to this argument, rainbow families often do not live isolated from other people. They often live close to their relatives, and as with any other family, sometimes relatives as well help with raising the child. Therefore, no matter if we are now talking about rainbow families, a single mother/father, or even 1 parent and a grandparent, the child does have both the masculine and the feminine role model in its life, in most cases.

Supporters of same-sex marriage often say that by allowing same-sex couples to get married, the children they are raising will be legally more secure and it will help them. MP Pavla Golasowská in her counter argument states that children growing up in rainbow families are not anyhow discriminated against, and they actually don't have any legal disadvantages from children with divorced opposite-sex parents (Golasowská 2023, June 29).

Some MPs also reminded others of existing Conventions that align with this framing.

"Moreover, the Convention on the Rights of the Child in Article 1, paragraph 1 speaks quite clearly, I quote: "Every child shall be registered immediately after birth and shall have the right from birth to a name, the right to acquire a nationality, and as far as possible, the right to know and be cared for by his or her parents." – **Marian Jurečka** (February 7, 2024)

The German MP Elisabeth Winkelmeier-Becker points out, regarding her view on adoption by same-sex couples, that in the adoption process, there are certain criteria that she sees as less important than the sex of the adoptive parents (Winkelmeier-Becker 2015, June 11). This point was not seen in the Czech discourse, despite that the importance of the male and female roles were seen as important as well. On the other hand, Winkelmeier-Becker (same as MP Bělohávková in Czechia) recognizes that LGBTQ people can also be good parents, however, she still sees as fit to ensure that the child will be brought up by one man and one woman, to give the child both the masculine and the feminine role (Winkelmeier-Becker 2015, June 11). MP Marcus Weinberg is of a similar opinion as MP Winkelmeier-Becker, and he would also like to make sure that the fact whether the child will have both roles (masculine and feminine) will be considered when adopting (Weinberg 2015, June 11).

“Children benefit from the stability of their parents' relationship. It is fundamentally in the interest of children to grow up in a stable partnership of their biological parents of both sexes. The fact that the connections between a man and a woman and between two same-sex partners are different here is not discriminatory but completely value-neutral; because these legal connections are different.” - Marcus Weinberg (June 11, 2024. Page 10450-10451)

German MP Alexander Hoffmann shares a similar view that the Czech MP Aleš Dufek mentioned in his statement, and that is that we should not look at this topic in a “self-fulfillment” type of way, but rather looking at the welfare of the child when dealing with adoption, regardless by whom (Hoffmann 2015, June 11)

This shows us that the outlook on this frame is quite similar both in Germany and Czechia. Both groups of MPs are urging others to put the welfare of the child before the individual wishes to adopt a child, claiming that the nuclear family is the type of family that leads to proper child development.

4.1.2 Lawlessness

No MP (neither in Germany nor in Czechia) has resorted to such extreme cases, such as the ones mentioned in the literature review from the past, to call supporters of same-sex marriage terrorists. However, in Czechia, there have been some calls that expressed their disapproval of the fact that the law would have to be changed, according to what the people say. MP Romana Bělohávková shared in her statement where she added that she is convinced that even though there might be developments or changes in society, the law should not be changing with those changes, instead, “*people must adapt to the law*” (Bělohávková 2023, June 2).

What was different from the Czech debate is that in the German one, a significant number of MPs were worried about whether the possible legalization of Ehe für Alle (same-sex marriage) would even be Constitutional or if it would go against any previous Court rulings. This goes back to the claim mentioned in Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper's (2009) paper, stating that some people frame their opposition to same-sex marriage in the way of upholding the current law and protection of the Constitution. A lot of times, the German MPs expressed their fears of possibly going against the Grundgesetz (Basic Law = Constitution). In Germany, certain developments when it comes to same-sex couples' rights were implemented through Courts. On the other hand, in Czechia we do not see such presence of Courts in this regard, therefore the German framing of the opposition and connecting it to the Court decisions is special in this way, and significantly more common and expected than in the Czech discourse.

According to the interview with MP Jürgen Klimke that I have done, he mentions that the interpretation of the Grundgesetz is very important to understand who voted how (Klimke in a personal interview, May 11, 2024). Him personally, he voted in favor of Ehe für Alle, due to the interpretation of the Grundgesetz that will be mentioned in the section talking about the frame "*does not go against the Basic Law*" below in the section discussing the frames in favor. On the other hand, the more common argument connected to this frame is the one that MP Christoph Bergner shared with me in our email conversation, where he mentioned that he voted against it due to contradictions with the Grundgesetz. He mentioned the Article 6 which puts marriage and family under the protection of the state (Grundgesetz, Art. 6, Para. 1) (Christoph Bergner, email direct message to Karel Mařík, March 3, 2024).

In the Parliamentary debates, MPs such as Alexander Hoffmann were quoting the 2013 Federal Constitutional Court's ruling that marriage is for one man and one woman (Hoffmann 2017, June 11). MP Thomas Silberhorn in his statement talks about the consistency of the FCC rulings regarding this topic, and mentions even a previous ruling from 2008. MP Silberhorn therefore showcases his position that the MPs should follow the rulings of the Court, that being both allowing stepchild adoption, but also respecting marriage as an institution between 1 man and 1 woman (Silberhorn 2013, December 19).

Another possible problem the German MPs are discussing is whether it is needed to amend the Constitution in order to legalize same-sex marriage, or if it's not necessary. MP Volker Kauder is among those who pointed out that the same ministry previously said that it was necessary to amend it, but now it's saying that it's not (Kauder 2017, June 30). MP Gerda Hasselfeldt later mentioned it too, and MP Elisabeth Winkelmeier-Becker added that going back, even the Code of Hammurabi talks about marriage

as man and woman (which is connected more closely to the *history frame*) (Winkelmeier-Becker 2013, December 19).

MP Elisabeth Winkelmeier-Becker is also convinced that since the Court (as already mentioned above) has stated that marriage has heterosexuality as its prerequisite, and is reserved only for one man and one woman, she is convinced that the change of the institution, the opening of marriage to same-sex couples, is not something that is in the hands of the MPs in the Bundestag (Winkelmeier-Becker 2015, June 19).

To show the main differences between Germany and Czechia regarding this frame, the German MPs mainly mention the Article 6 of the Grundgesetz (Basic Law/Constitution) as being the possible obstacle to legalizing same-sex marriage, as well as one of the reasons why they are opposed to it. When it comes to Czechia, the lawlessness frame was indeed mentioned, but not quite in the same way as in Germany, because the arguments were not revolving around the Constitution to this extent.

“Article 6 of the Basic Law places marriage and family under the special protection of the state. The concept of marriage is not defined and therefore must be interpreted necessarily by the consistent jurisprudence of the Constitutional Court. Marriage is thus the community of life between man and woman, based on free decision and equality.” – Dr. Volker Ullrich (February 18, 2016. Page 15279)

4.1.3 Slippery slope

Many times the Czech Christian Democratic MPs frame their negative stance about the wishes of LGBTQ people for same-sex marriage in this way – according to those holding this position, when there was a debate about registered partnerships around 20 years ago, LGBTQ activists and those pushing for legalization of such institute promised that it is the *last thing* they will want, meaning no adoption, no marriage, just some kind of legal recognition. After this argument often comes the fear that it will not stop here. This means that in a few years there might be wishes to legalize for instance polygamy. To provide a bit of an opposition to this framing, some politicians and the public, in the more general (not only Christian Democratic) discourse, do argue back saying that the fact that some people might have promised something possibly on behalf of the whole LGBTQ community (*it is not a homogenate organization that would have one centralized decision making body*), does not mean that LGBTQ people should not have any more rights. People who are now asking for same-sex marriage often were not even born when the debate about registered partnerships was happening, therefore that argument should not be applied to the current people who are pushing for same-sex marriage.

MP Nina Nováková is one of those framing it in the way, where she mentions the situation 20 years ago, and leads her argument from there.

“When our predecessors decided to approve the law on registered partnerships less than twenty years ago, some said – from those who longed to be able to enter into a registered partnership, i.e., representatives of same-sex couples or their advocates – they said: This is the last step we want. We simply want some form of official recognition, some official acknowledgment of this union.” – Nina Nováková (June 1, 2023)

However, she is not the only one using this frame. MPs Aleš Dufek, Pavla Golasowská, and Romana Bělohávková were some of the Czech MPs who brought the possibility of polygamy to the discourse, proving the already established framing which was mentioned even in Hull’s (2001) and McFarland’s (2011) papers. Pavla Golasowská frames it according to the logic of love being the core of marriage, not reproduction, polygamy might become part of discussion in the future too (Golasowská 2023, June 29), therefore allowing same-sex marriage has to be stopped. She adds to it that if we now remove the need for the partners to be man and woman, she is convinced that in the future we might also remove the fact that marriage has to be only 2 people (Golasowská 2023, June 29). MP Golasowská mentions this because she does not see *love* as the prerequisite of marriage, but instead *reproduction*. That can happen between 1 woman and 1 man. And if someone sees *love* as the prerequisite, then they might wish to open the institution of marriage even further in the future (Golasowská 2023, June 29), by which she is pointing directly at the slippery slope frame, meaning that love between multiple people is also love, therefore polygamic marriage might follow after same-sex marriage. But the MP that argued within this frame the most in the Czech discourse was Romana Bělohávková.

“When the law on registered partnerships was passed in 2006, I remember the discussion very well, it was also turbulent, difficult, and there were words that this was the maximum. Adoption of children? Not a chance. Marriage? We hadn't even thought of that. Fifteen years have passed, and marriage for all has become a topic. But I know that even this is not the final topic. Another fifteen years will pass, and some of you, perhaps, will still be here, but I certainly won't, and there will perhaps be consideration of a law that allows polyamory. And believe me, it will happen. Because when you look west of our borders, there are countries in the world where, just as we are now dealing with marriage for all, they are seriously dealing with marriage for multiple people simultaneously. And perhaps in another fifteen years, it will go even further. I don't know.” - Romana Bělohávková (June 1, 2023)

Romana Bělohávková adds to this argument that same-sex couples might possibly become the preferred couples regarding adoption, therefore opposite-sex couples would not be the priority anymore (Bělohávková 2023, June 1).

An interesting comparison was mentioned by the MP Nina Nováková, who was among the most visible opponents in the debates about same-sex marriage in the Chamber of Deputies. She compared the wishes to legalize same-sex marriage to certain attempts to attack fundamental institutions (such as marriage) that are essential to society. According to her framing, same-sex marriage wishes are similar to Marxist-Leninist regimes, leading to totalitarianism (Nováková 2023, June 1).

Regarding the *slippery slope* frame in the German discourse, there was no argument that was worth mentioning regarding possible redefinitions of marriage to a polygamous institution, as it was often mentioned in the Czech discourse. But even though there was no framing about slippery slope in the Parliamentary debates, it does not mean that it is a non-existent frame in the German discourse and that the Czech debate would be strange in this aspect. MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann briefly mentioned that he does hear this argument.

“Yes, it hurts when some opponents suggest that the step from opening marriage to same-sex couples to other undesirable connections is not far.” – Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (June 11, 2015. Page 10446)

We can see that the comparison between the German and Czech discourse regarding this frame can be drawn very clearly. While the Czech Christian Democratic MPs framed their disapproval in this *slippery slope* frame, which is likely to stir emotions and fear in the voters, the German MPs used other, more practical, reasons to show their disapproval of same-sex marriage. Among the most widely used ones was the framing above, about the possible unconstitutionality of the proposal.

4.1.4 Religion

The religious frame was, contrary to my initial expectations when deciding to write about this topic, not the most widely used frame in Czechia. What’s more, it was one of those that was used rather rarely. However, it can be debated to what extent is the framing “*one man and one woman / history*” connected to the religious frame.

For Hayato Okamura, as he shares his personal experience with marriage, and for him being Christian and traditional, the religious history of marriage between a man and a woman is very important. While agreeing that even certain Christian Churches do allow same-sex marriage, the majoritarian opinion is rather in disagreement (Okamura 2023).

MP Nováková's statement below can be looked at in both the historical frame, but also the religious frame. These two are often used in the same argument by other MPs as well. Here, MP Nováková talks about our history and culture, and mentions that the culture is based on Christianity (Nováková 2023, June 1). Therefore, the main frame through which she is looking at it is not clear, if I was to connect it only to simply just one of my established frames. But since religion is mentioned, adding it to the *religious framing* section felt more natural.

"Now I come to the point that some of us oppose the idea that the concept of marriage, and with it, the concept that was reserved for a certain social institution, which was proven, and in Western culture, I emphasize, in Western culture, which is based on antiquity and Christianity, basically its model has not changed, and it is such an Aristotelian one, as mentioned by Mr. Major through the chairmanship, Mr. Major somewhat mentioned it." - **Nina Nováková** (June 1, 2023)

Aleš Dufek contributed to the discussion with his view, which was that the discussion about same-sex marriage should not be looked at through a religious lens (Dufek 2023, June 2). Instead, he is framing his arguments in different ways, falling under multiple of the frames in this paper.

Considering the fact that Germany has a higher share of the population that is religious (in the case of this paper, people who are Christian), I expected there to be more opposition to same-sex marriage using the religious framing. While some MPs did in fact mention their religious beliefs as the reason for their opposition, what was very surprising to me was that some MPs even used their religious beliefs to explain their support for same-sex marriage (more described later in the paper). With the general explanation that it is a Christian conservative value to want to spend one's life with their significant other, caring for each other and being responsible for each other. This framing is therefore very different from the Czech case. In Czechia, when religion is used in the Christian Democratic discourse, it likely means opposition to same-sex marriage, as we saw above. The German Christian Democrats therefore opened a new way to a possible framing, that some Czech Christian Democrats could adopt, in case some do support same-sex marriage.

I was able to find these mentioned arguments also in the sources and personal interviews from the MPs that I managed to reach. Although these do not come from the Parliamentary debate, they are worth mentioning. MP Jürgen Klimke mentions that it is likely that an MP who represents a conservative Christian constituency will vote against same-sex marriage. Due to the fact that parties are attempting to appeal to their local voters and their opinions, even though sometimes their personal views might differ (Klimke in a personal interview, May 11, 2024).

MP Peter Tauber mentions on his blog one interesting comparison, that could somewhat explain the differences in voting despite the MPs often being religious. In his blog (that he shared with me in our email conversation), he explains his support of same-sex marriage from his Protestant point of view, saying that for Catholics, marriage is a Holy Sacrament. On the contrary, for Protestants, it is not. (Tauber 2017). This could possibly explain why the remaining CDU/CSU MPs did not vote in favor, or even why the Czech KDU-ČSL MPs voted against because in Czechia, Catholicism is more present than Protestantism.

Moving on to the German Bundestag debates, here, the MP Helmut Brandt was one of those who mentioned religion in his speech.

“It may also be that there is no legal definition for the term marriage, but – as Ms. Winkelmeier-Becker has already explained – there is a history, and there are many cultural and religious reasons that have led to the concept of marriage, as we and I understand it.” - Helmut Brandt (June 11, 2015. Page 10441)

On the other hand, Volker Kauder shares that he is not in favor of same-sex marriage, likely also due to religious reasons, but on the other hand, he mentions that using religion, it can be also framed in a different way that will be in favor of same-sex marriage (Kauder 2017, June 30), as briefly showed in the previous paragraph, or even more in the section discussing separation of Church and state.

To sum up this frame, among the opponents of same-sex marriage who frame their opposition in the *religious frame*, their arguments (whether in Czechia or Germany) do not differ too much. The only difference is that the German MPs used the *religious frame* even in support, not only in opposition. That is a clear and significant difference between these two Christian Democratic parties, in this aspect. An interesting point worth pointing out is that the MPs do not use the argument about morality of same-sex relationships, in connection to the religious frame, as was mentioned as an example in Liebler, Schwartz, and Harper’s (2009) work in my literature review.

4.1.5 One man and one woman / history of marriage

The discussion about opening marriage to same-sex couples is heavily influenced by the history of the institution. Many MPs, both in Germany and Czechia, are framing their opposition exactly in this, more of a traditionalist, way. For them, the institution of marriage has gained a lot of meaning with time, and

they wish to preserve it in this way for the future. For instance, MP Aleš Dufek thinks too many people see the long history of marriage as important, for it to be taken lightly (Dufek 2023, June 1).

Marriage as the union of a man and a woman has lasted for thousands of years. It was so in slave societies, it was so in feudalism, it was so in past centuries, it was so under communism and Nazism, even though there were various systems that initially came up with different experiments. But in the end, even these monstrous systems realized that for society to function, the basic unit must be a family based on marriage, on the relationship between a man and a woman. That's all.” – Aleš Dufek (June 29, 2023)

To MP Dufek’s argument, MP Hayato Okamura adds that for those who live in marriage, the current legal definition and the history in general have value and should not be therefore changed to mean something else (Okamura 2023, June 29).

Quite frequently for those who frame their disapproval in the way “*one man, one woman*”, they add that they are however not against other forms of cohabitation, but since the word marriage means exactly “one man and one woman,” they do not see a way for it to open for same-sex couples.

A rather humorous framing of the arguments came from MP Šimon Heller, where he said that “*beef is beef here, chicken is chicken. Everything has its names. For me, marriage will always remain a union between a man and a woman*” (Heller 2023, June 29).

MP Jiří Navrátil, who came up with the amendment (so-called “third way” – mentioned later in this paper) to the proposal of same-sex marriage, combines both frames (one man, one woman / history) together in his speech, where he explains that the word marriage is important for traditional people, and therefore also for his KDU-ČSL party, and talks about that it has always been just one man, one woman, even in the times of Mesopotamia (Navrátil 2023, June 29).

When framing arguments, the German MPs talk frequently about the significance of marriage being an institution for one woman and one man as well. This is often described as something that has been here for a long time, therefore the public has developed a certain relationship with the institution thanks to its history. That means that these 2 frames (*history* and *one man + one woman*) are very often connected even in the German discourse. Usually with one comes the other, therefore the German case confirmed that having them both in just one section in fact does make sense. As one of the possible examples of this interconnectedness, MP Volker Kauder shares his argument:

“It is also not about whether love, loyalty, and attention can be lived in relationships between same-sex partners. It simply boils down to whether the concept of marriage, which has been defined in our cultural sphere for centuries as the union of a man and a woman, will now also be opened up. All I can say is: It is already clear to me that this is not the same, which is why it is quite justified to define the term "marriage" as a relationship between a man and a woman.” - Volker Kauder (June 30, 2017. Page 25107)

MP Thomas Silberhorn agrees with MP Kauder’s framing and mentions that the proposal of same-sex marriage will destroy marriage as one man and one woman (Silberhorn 2013, December 19).

Going slightly back to previous frames, another frame that is often connected to the *historical* frame is the *religious* frame. However, the presence of the frame *history* and *one man and one woman* was more prevalent, which is why I decided to mention it here. As an example of the combination of the two, MP Elisabeth Winkelmeier-Becker goes back to the definitions of marriage when inventing the Civil Code or the Code of Hammurabi, but adds that it is not only history but also culture and religion (in relation to Adam and Eve) that shaped the institution of marriage, therefore we should not change it (Winkelmeier-Becker 2013, December 19).

Having mentioned the *protection* of marriage as one argument in this frame in my literature review, supporters of this argument say that we need to protect marriage in the form of one man and one woman. Opponents of this often ask what exactly should we protect it from, and what or who threatens it?

To this argument, the Czech MP Pavla Golasowská has an answer, and that is that if the change of the definition of marriage changed (from being an institution of *one man and one woman* to an institution of *two people*), it *“would naturally affect all marriages, both existing and future ones.”* (Golasowská 2023, June 29). MP Golasowská also acknowledges that already today, there are many marriages who unfortunately do not work out, and the divorce rate is quite high. But as the solution, she does not see opening marriage to same-sex couples, and she does feel like it should be protected regardless (Golasowská 2023, June 29).

Both parties, the Czech KDU-ČSL and the German sister parties CDU/CSU, can be looked at as Christian Democratic parties who are rather conservative and traditional, therefore the focus on *history / one man and one woman* (and additionally *religion*) is expected to be present in their views and statements. When it comes to these frames, the statements did not differ much in the countries, since in both countries the MPs are discussing that marriage has always been this way, and from this viewpoint comes their

opposition to it. Plus, in both countries, there was the presence of the interconnectedness of the 2 frames of *history* and *one man and one woman*, which, again, confirms the choice to merge them into one chapter.

4.1.6 Reproduction as a core of marriage

Before having done any research, I did not think of this frame as potentially being used many times, but contrary to my expectations, for a lot of Czech Christian Democratic MPs, reproduction is, in fact, the core of marriage, therefore their unanimous negative position towards same-sex marriage is clearer when considering this frame.

As one of the framers, MP Nina Nováková (similar as MP Winkelmeier-Becker in the German discourse regarding the protection of children) in her statement agrees that heterosexuality does not automatically make someone a good parent, but she still prefers a traditional form of family, due to the historical reasons and mainly the possibility of reproduction of opposite-sex couples. She adds that it is the best form because it does not involve any state interference when creating a family (Nováková 2023, June 1). As well as MP Nina Nováková, MP Pavla Golasowská counts with the possibility of reproduction as a necessity when debating about marriage, and to that she adds that the core of marriage should not be *love*, but as this chapter suggests, *reproduction* (Golasowská 2023, June 29).

A lot of the time, supporters of same-sex marriage argue back that we allow old couples or infertile heterosexual couples to get married, even if they are not planning to have children. And that we should either ensure that the people who intend to get married are planning children, or that we do not allow them to get married either, according to the frame that reproduction is the core of marriage. That puts the debate in a tricky situation. MP Pavla Golasowská acknowledges this argument but does not share it. And she provides her reasoning:

“The third argument is: why shouldn't same-sex couples be able to marry when some heterosexual couples also cannot or do not want to have children, yet they can still marry? While a heterosexual couple can theoretically conceive a child at any time, and it cannot be completely ruled out in advance, with same-sex couples, we know in advance with certainty that they can never conceive children. Therefore, there is no reason why the legal institution of marriage, which was created and is primarily intended for procreation and the subsequent upbringing of children, should include couples who cannot conceive a child together, and thus will not do so.” - Pavla Golasowská (June 29, 2023)

MP Golasowská's framing is very similar to the statement by Manfred Spieker (2015, as cited in Fritzsche and Lang 2019), where he also talks about the possibility, the potential to conceive a child, when we are talking about a heterosexual couple.

Looking at the Czech discourse, *reproduction as a core of marriage* was from my research one of the top frames in the Czech discourse in the Parliamentary debates. Interestingly, we do not see such support for the frame in Germany. Certainly, it has been a widely used one, but not to the extent as in Czechia. MP Alexander Hoffmann in his speech acknowledges that even same-sex couples can provide a good environment for a child, but for him, the reproduction aspect is the crucial difference between same-sex partnerships and opposite-sex marriage (Hoffmann 2016). MP Gerda Hasselfeldt is also among those who expressed their disapproval of same-sex marriage because she is of the opinion that marriage “*is and remains ... the foundation for the continued existence of our society*” (Hasselfeldt 2017, June 30. Page 25114). And MP Marcus Weinberg frames his opposition in the way his Czech colleague MP Golasowská did, regarding the *possibility* of having a child, when it comes to heterosexual couples (Weinberg 2015, June 11. Page 10450).

4.1.7 Lack of public support

Supporters of same-sex marriage often say that there is majoritarian support in the country (at the time of the debates, both in Germany and in Czechia there was majoritarian support of same-sex marriage) to legalize same-sex marriage, and that is why the representatives should legalize it - as the will of the people. The Czech MP Hayato Okamura has a different outlook on public support. Not country-based, but instead world-based, claiming that around the world, most people still see marriage as one man and one woman (Okamura 2023, June 1).

MP Nina Nováková shared that the voters have been texting her that the debate about same-sex marriage came at a bad time (Nováková 2023, June 29). This argument can be very often seen especially in comment sections on social media, showing that it is a very common one, especially in the public. It is being framed that the MPs should debate about more important things than same-sex marriage. It is natural that for people who are not affected by what is being debated, it is always a “waste” of time. However, the Parliament is able to discuss multiple things at once. Not just one.

In Germany, this framing also resembles the Czech way of framing. MPs both from the CDU/CSU and the KDU-ČSL mentioned that they are not certain whether the popular support really is that high. It is an argument you can hear quite often. Framers of this argument say that it can either be because the opinion polls are not independent, or the number can be misleading, because some people do not feel comfortable sharing their opposition towards same-sex marriage, fearing negative reactions from their surroundings. In the German case, it is the MP Helmut Brandt who mentions these concerns and doubts about the extent of public support, due to fears of being perceived as homophobes. He adds that these people are discriminated against, for not being able to share their opinion freely (Brandt 2015, June 11. Page 10441).

Despite some MPs sharing their counter arguments claiming that the public support did in fact rise (which will be mentioned in the *in favor* section later in this paper), the German MP Alexander Hoffmann, regarding this frame, is still convinced that “*societal understanding of marriage has not changed*” (Hoffmann 2016, November 10. Page 19900).

4.2 New frames used against same-sex marriage

Since the research for this paper included data from the early 2000s, it is logical that there will be certain frames that had been used more frequently back in the day and nowadays they are not so prevalent. With that comes that there will also be newly emerged frames *against* in the discourse about same-sex marriage, that were not present or popular back then but have only emerged recently with the developing debate about the topic. Certain new frames can be more prevalent for the German case, and some for the Czech, meaning that they can also be more of a local nature. However, the already previously existing frames are mostly the main ones that occur the most throughout the debates. Despite that, there were a few mentions about new frames, that deserve to be mentioned.

4.2.1 There is no right for marriage and no right for a child

When conducting my literature review, there had been mentions of this frame, however, I decided to see it as a sub-frame of the *lawlessness* frame. Nevertheless, after conducting my actual research for the empirical part of my paper, the usage of the words “*there is no right for a child*” was very common, especially in the Czech discourse, so I decided to add it as a separate frame. This frame can be seen as a reaction to the *civil rights / human rights* frame which generally holds the view that all people should have the same rights. However, this frame suggests that there is no *right* for gay marriage or for children.

Many people also say that LGBTQ people already do have the right to get married and that no one is stopping them, but only if they marry the opposite sex.

Although in Germany, certain statements could be considered to fall under this frame, in my research I decided to add them to a different (already existing) frame, because, in the Czech discourse, the statements were substantially more directly addressing the fact that there is no right to get married, or to get a child.

From the Parliamentary debates, MP Šimon Heller in his statement shares that a child is a gift from God, and even some of his friends who wished to become parents, unfortunately, could not. Therefore, he does not see children as a right, but as God's gift (Heller 2023, June 2). Even the MP Bělohávková is convinced that there is no right for a child, connecting her view with the resolution of the European Court (Bělohávková 2023, June 29). A rather hyperbolic comparison regarding rights for marriage/children came from the MP Marek Výborný:

“This debate isn't about rights, but it's primarily about values because marriage itself isn't a right. If I were to metaphorically compare it now, do I have the right to be a footballer for FC Barcelona? I think that's not a right; it's a path that someone, who has talent, opportunities, and often luck, takes. Similarly, marriage isn't a right, and its purpose isn't to regulate the relationship between two people who love each other. Love is something different from rights.” – Marek Výborný (June 1, 2023)

4.2.2 Equality without marriage

This is another new frame, that most likely gained significance with the emergence of same-sex partnerships, which gave same-sex couples more rights than they had before. And due to the fact that some MPs see marriage and partnership as a different thing (therefore marriage can't be opened for same-sex couples), for these MPs, the institutions already are equal (or will be equal once certain minor changes in the rights sphere are made).

Some MPs, such as Pavla Golasowská in Czechia, have said that same-sex couples are equal already because they can already enter marriage, however, only if they marry a person of the opposite sex (Golasowská 2023, June 29). Others framed their viewpoint in the way that it certainly is important to equalize marriage and partnerships (without the adoption rights) and the fact that same-sex couples will have their own institution (partnership), does not make them any less equal of partners. MP Aleš Dufek in Czechia is one of the framers of the latter:

“This government intends to equalize persons of the same sex, which means that we have an intention to address these issues, such as joint property of spouses, widow's pension, which have been mentioned here, so that same-sex couples also receive the same rights as traditional spouses in these matters.” – Aleš Dufek (June 1, 2023)

Among the supporters of same-sex marriage, you can hear voices that agree with this framing, and they are satisfied, as long as they get the same rights, but the disagreement with this framing is more visible in the general discourse. Despite the fact that the institutions would indeed be equal in terms of rights (excluding adoption rights), the fact that there are 2 different institutions (marriage and partnership) still feels discriminatory to many people.

MP Nina Nováková goes further with the equality framing and shares in her statement that homosexual people do not face discrimination. As the reasoning for this claim, she uses the fact that we see LGBTQ people in high positions, and in the Parliament (Nováková 2023, June 1).

In the German Bundestag, there also have been quite a few MPs who argued that they would like to achieve equality for LGBTQ people and same-sex couples, but these MPs do not share the majoritarian parliamentary opinion that it should be through the opening of marriage for same-sex couples. Instead, these MPs say that they would support other laws that will ensure the equality of partnerships and marriage, but they would not redefine what marriage means. The reason for this, overall, is that both forms of partnership are different, therefore there can't be just one institution for them. Framers of this argument do not agree with the *discrimination of a certain group* argument (included in *history / one man and one woman* frame) that says that having 2 separate institutions is discriminatory. Instead, MP Elisabeth Winkelmeier-Becker (2015, June 11) sees no problem with having 2 distinct institutions. Along with others, MP Dr. Sabine Sütterlin-Waack is of the opinion that discrimination does not mean that same-sex couples will not have access to marriage, and that even though there would be 2 separate institutions, the state should support both (Sütterlin-Waack 2016, November 10).

Regarding *equality without marriage*, MP Dr. Sütterlin-Waack also proposes that some “third way”, or middle ground could be done here, which would show in the Constitution that both marriage and partnerships would be supported by the state (Sütterlin-Waack 2016, November 10), and it would ensure satisfaction on both sides and will not be discriminatory towards anyone, because they would be equal, but separate. MP Heribert Hirte also lightly touched on the topic of the third way, that a change of the word “married” could happen, and it would be more inclusive, because it would contain partnerships as

well (Hirte 2017, May 17). And again, leading to a middle ground that could be a good compromise for all. The reason why I did not incorporate them into the next new frame (*the third way*) is that it is more directly connected specifically to the proposal of the third way, a concept that is more relevant to the Czech discourse.

MP Alexander Hoffmann raises an interesting point, that opening marriage to same-sex couples, without the absolute support of the public, does not do justice to same-sex couples. He mentions some countries (such as the US or Mexico) in which it was the Supreme Court that legalized same-sex marriage, but the country lacks for instance anti-discriminatory laws for LGBTQ people in the workplace (Hoffmann 2016, May 17). Therefore, MP Hoffmann suggests focusing on combating discrimination, and going towards equality, but is convinced that marriage is not the one milestone that will get them there. But regardless, he does underline the fact that he does want full equality, which he in his other statement explains as “*treating different things equally*” (Hoffmann 2017, May 10. Page 23555).

“All of us here want exactly the same thing: 100 percent equality. We differ in the way to achieve it. You say: We achieve 100 percent equality only when civil partnerships are also called marriage. We say: We understand equality as a process. We make legislative changes step by step - wherever there is a need.” - Alexander Hoffmann (May 10, 2017. Page 23555)

As his ground argument for this way of framing, MP Hoffmann mentions the fact that some same-sex couples wish for equal rights, but they do not need to have the same name for their relationship (Hoffmann 2015, June 11).

The main difference between framing arguments in this way, in Germany and Czechia, is that in Czechia, there have been more direct claims about the fact that same-sex couples are already equal, even though not all Czech MPs viewed it this way, and acknowledge the current inequality. However, in Germany, the general agreement is that equality has not happened yet, but they are striving for it, but some MPs can’t agree on how to get there.

4.2.3 The third way

The last new framing worth mentioning (specifically in the Czech discourse) is the so-called “third way,” which is basically a compromise proposal that ended up being the one that passed through the legislative process in the latest debate in 2024. As already mentioned, it is the one that excludes the adoption rights and excludes the name *marriage* but includes other rights. And in the debates in this legislative period,

the Czech Christian Democrats repeated it very often, since they saw it as a good compromise for both parties (in favor and against same-sex marriage). That compromise would not cross the boundaries of the conservative parties such as the Christian Democrats, but would also give more rights to same-sex couples. This means that since the proposal came from the KDU-ČSL (the Christian Democrats), they saw themselves as the mediators, the ones that managed to pass “at least something,” so that everyone is partially happy about the result.

This frame comes often with the saying “just don’t call it marriage.” MP Hayato Okamura calls this *third-way* argument as “perfectly acceptable,” considering his Christian faith (Okamura 2023, June 29). MP Romana Bělohávková shares exactly the same opinion, that it is a good compromise, that includes most of the rights the institution of marriage has.

“I really think the time has come to adjust some legislative parameters of what has so far been called registered partnership. And we, as the KDU-ČSL, even though it may surprise many, have prepared a middle way. ... In this proposal, 90% of what those who call for marriage for all want to change is really addressed”. – Romana Bělohávková (June 1, 2023)

In Germany, this frame has not been as frequent as in the Czech discourse, where there was a bigger need to find a compromise, since not all other parties (except for the Christian Democrats) were in full agreement about same-sex marriage. Therefore, in Czechia, the talks about the *third way* were more necessary, in order to pass something, rather than nothing. Some German MPs did mention the third way, or common ground, very similarly to how the Czech Christian Democrats did, however, I decided to include these arguments to the previous frame (*equality without marriage*). But indeed, these two frames are very similar and could be merged into a common one.

4.3 Frames used in favor of same-sex marriage

This part of the paper will have a different structure than the previous part which addresses the frames against same-sex marriage. The reason for this is that there had been no Czech Christian Democratic MPs who expressed their support for same-sex marriage, therefore I had no data that I could use to compare their statements to their German colleagues. However, this alone can stand as the biggest comparison when it comes to the approaches to same-sex marriage - the fact that in a Christian Democratic party in the German Bundestag, there are supporters of same-sex marriage, but in the Czech Chamber of Deputies there are not. This means that in this part, I will be able to only analyze how the German Christian Democrats talk about same-sex marriage, keeping in mind the frames that I identified

based on my literature review. Which will make the frames shorter in length. Same as for the part that talks about the opposition to same-sex marriage, even in this part, there were some newly emerged frames of arguments that will be listed below under the already existing frames.

4.3.1 Civil rights / human rights

Interestingly enough, this frame is not so popular among the MPs in Germany, as I thought that the frame of human and civil rights would be more prevalent in their context. However, I could not find any statement from the CDU/CSU MPs in the German Bundestag that would directly frame their support using exactly this frame. This shows the MPs, even though this might be their reasoning for support, frame it in a different way, for instance regarding the Constitution, which I will mention in this part more in detail.

Comparing it back to the Czech case, it makes the debate seem quite similar in this regard, since in Czechia the statements revolved more around the argument it is *not* a human / civil right to get married or have children.

4.3.2 Equality

Keeping in mind the previous section discussing frames against same-sex marriage, it is noticeable that the approach to equality is often different from what I imagined this frame would include. For many MPs, equality does not mean the name of the institution being the same (“marriage”), but instead, it is about what rights are inside of the institutions. Still, there have been some MPs in Germany who do believe that same-sex couples should be able to get married and achieve equality by that, including the name. MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann stated in his argument that there should be no different names for the institutions, because by automatically saying “partnered” and “married,” it does not give individuals the freedom to decide whether they want to share with others who they love, or not (Kaufmann 2016). In his follow-up argument, he touches on the fact that other Catholic countries already legalized same-sex marriage, including the name, and that “*equal love deserves the same name*” (Kaufmann 2016, February 18. Page 15276). In my literature review, I mentioned the statement by Marie Jílková (2023) where she also mentions that there is only one form of love, therefore we can see that this framing is used even in the Parliamentary debates.

4.3.3 Discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens

Tolerance was mentioned many times during the German debates. What is interesting to point out in this aspect is that very often this framing was coming even from the opponents of same-sex marriage, who usually do want the same rights for same-sex couples, but at the same time are skeptical towards calling the relationships *marriage*, because they see those two as two separate institutions. However, just a few MPs framed their argument using the tolerance frame on the supporting side. I managed to contact one of those who frame their support in this way, MP Dr. Heribert Hirte. He advised me to look at his social media, and I found an article that interviewed him. In his interview conducted by *domradio.de*, MP Hirte mentioned that we should allow same-sex couples to get married out of respect for each person, and by not doing so, it is hurting people, which he sees as wrong (Hirte 2017). This falls therefore under the discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens. And among those in the Parliamentary debates who did support same-sex marriage is MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak, who framed his support in this way.

“We have always been the ones who bring together new developments with traditional values. I am convinced: today we can set an important signal for a modern, tolerant, but also genuinely value-conservative policy, not only for society but also for the Union parties.” – Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak (June 30, 2017. Page 25112)

MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann is also among the supporters, and mentions the importance to not only the people who would be able to get married, but it would also have an impact on their immediate circle, their friends, and family (Kaufmann 2015, June 11).

Regarding discrimination, MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann also pointed out an interesting aspect of having 2 separate institutions based on who you are in a relationship with (this was already slightly mentioned in the *equality* frame, but I believe it deserves to be mentioned in both of these frames). When you are filling out questionnaires about yourself, often you provide your relationship status. In the case of opposite-sex couples, you can write down “married”. When it comes to same-sex couples, in countries that do not have same-sex marriage, these couples have only the option to write down “registered” or “partnered” (Kaufmann 2015, June 11). The same is true on personal identification cards. As MP Kaufmann correctly points out, this, for some people might be uncomfortable, in case they do not wish to disclose their private relationship in public. But this difference gives them no other option. This is the

same in Czechia, and some actors (outside the Christian Democratic discourse) have been pointing it out as well.

“Yes, in the end, it may only be about terminology from a legal perspective. But when you truthfully indicate “civil partnered” on forms or applications, every authority or employer immediately knows how you love; ... Many simply do not want to say that they are civil partnered. They want to say that they are married, that they are spouses.” - Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (June 11, 2015. Page 10446)

4.3.4 Separation of Church and state

Contrary to the Parliamentary debate in Czechia, the framing of the argument about the separation of Church and state was indeed brought up in the German discourse. This can also be explained because there were no calls in favor of same-sex marriage in the Czech discourse, therefore the likelihood of framing their argument using this frame is lower. In Germany, however, there were arguments that since we are talking about the civil marriage (*Zivilehe*), not the religious institution of marriage, therefore the state can open civil marriage even to same-sex couples, without “forcing” Churches to do the same, unless some Churches want to. In the interview by *domradio.de* MP Dr. Heribert Hirte mentions that it is important to make the distinction between *Zivilehe* and religious marriage (Hirte 2017). MP Klimke also mentioned it in the interview I conducted with him. In the Parliamentary debates, it was MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann who brought it up in his speech.

“In conclusion, it's also not about questioning the sacrament of marriage. But it must be the right of the secular state to legislate its own non-discriminatory definition of marriage.” - Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (June 11, 2015. Page 10447)

Not directly linked to the separation of Church and state, but definitely connected to religious views, MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann framed religion (in this case he mentioned Jesus) in the way that would explain his support for same-sex marriage. Therefore, he took the *religious* frame, but framed it to be in favor of the proposal.

“Jesus showed us precisely this aspect, and he faced both approval and rejection for it. But this makes us listen: Who determines where love should go and what can or cannot be called love? And what makes those so sure who seem to know exactly where the boundary is? This is it, ladies and gentlemen, dear colleagues: It's about love, about lived responsibility, and about values.” - Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (February 18, 2016. Page 15275)

Continuing with the connection to support of same-sex marriage framed in a religious way, in an interview by *domradio.de*, the German MP Dr. Heribert Hirte supports same-sex marriage because he

believes that God accepts people as they are, and that responsibility for each other is a Christian idea of marriage (Hirte 2017). This framing is therefore very different from the Czech case. In Czechia, when religion is used in the Christian Democratic discourse, it likely means opposition to same-sex marriage, as we saw above. The German Christian Democrats therefore opened a new way to a possible framing, that some Czech Christian Democrats could adopt, in case some do support same-sex marriage.

4.3.5 Not a threat

The frame *not a threat* is often used as a reaction to the *historical frame* that the opposition mentions. Opponents of same-sex marriage frequently see the proposal as something that is there to disrupt something they have known to be in a certain way for a long time (in this case marriage being between one woman and one man), and now someone suddenly wants to change it. The framers of the *not a threat* frame argue back to the opponents that the *thing* that they have known is not actually going anywhere. Often, the supporters of same-sex marriage even add to this that the *thing* (in this case the institution of marriage) is not being devaluated, but instead underscored, since it is a popular thing and more people are expressing wishes to *enjoy* it.

MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak frames his support in a way that same-sex marriage is not going to threaten the institution of marriage, because it will not lead to a decrease of childbirth or a decrease in new heterosexual marriages (2017). He also adds the phrase that is popular in the Czech discourse (general discourse, not only Christian Democratic), which I mentioned in my literature review, and that is that “*Nothing is taken from one group by enabling another*” (Luczak 2017, June 30. Page 25112) - meaning enabling another to get married. On top of this argument, he added the position of The Evangelical Church, which sees it the same, that by allowing more people to enter marriage, the institution is underscored (Luczak 2017, June 30). This means that according to him, the institution of marriage might only gain from the legalization of same-sex marriage, since more people would be able to enjoy it than up until now. Dr. Stefan Kaufmann has the same opinion about in fact it strengthening marriage, rather than devaluating it (Kaufmann 2016, February 18).

4.3.6 Protection of children/children’s well-being

Contrary to my initial expectations, this frame has not been used as much as I thought, since I believe this frame can be used by the supporters of same-sex marriage in a successful way. Because the

opponents say they are against it due to the children protection, the counterargument regarding the protection of children therefore can be used to say that children in rainbow families would also somehow benefit from the legalization. And the different ways to frame their argument regarding the *protection of children*, which McFarland (2011) mentions and I mentioned in my literature review (such as that legalizing same-sex marriage might help to legally stabilize rainbow families which would bring security to the children), was not really used, despite my expectations. Mental health improvements following the legalization of same-sex marriage was not used either. However, Dr. Stefan Kaufmann was the one who brought up the children's welfare in his speech. Just in a different way.

“Regarding adoption rights. This is not about the right or entitlement of couples wanting to adopt, not even for heterosexuals. It is solely about whether same-sex couples should be included in an individual assessment or not. So, indeed, it's about the child and its well-being, about the child's right to the best parents.” - Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (June 11, 2015. Page 10447)

4.3.7 Expansion of conservative ideals

This frame is popularly used by the then British Prime Minister David Cameron, as mentioned in the literature review part. As far as the Czech discourse is concerned, it has not been used there, but going back to the German case, MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak was the one who used it in his speech. Framers of this argument are sending out signals to their fellow conservative MPs (but also to the general public as well) that even some conservative politicians around the world are supportive of same-sex marriage, and it is like that in Germany as well. In this statement, MP Luczak used almost directly Mr. Cameron's wording, to show his support - it being that his support is not contrary to him being a conservative Christian Democrat, but instead he says it is that way rather because of that (Luczak 2017, June 30). By using this frame, conservative MPs are explaining their support from a conservative point of view. Because marriage can be seen as a conservative institution since it talks about only two people, and about them staying faithful to each other and being responsible for each other.

“If we decide today to open marriage, we are implementing a piece of civic and conservative policy. Therefore, I particularly address my own faction, those who are still struggling, those who are still unsure how to vote today: Take the plunge! We have always been the ones to combine new developments with traditional values. I am convinced: Today, we can set an important sign for a modern, tolerant, but also genuinely value-conservative policy, not just for society but also for the Union parties.” - Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak (June 30, 2017. Page 25112)

He was not the only MP that frames his support in this way. In the *domradio.de* interview, MP Dr. Heribert Hirte also talks about it, that according to him, it is conservative to take responsibility for the other person in marriage (Hirte 2017).

4.4 New frames used in favor of same-sex marriage

4.4.1 Public support

The situation has changed since the time that my data in the literature review comes from, and therefore now I can add this frame to this paper. This frame talks about the fact that nowadays, the support for same-sex marriage is significantly higher than it used to be. Speaking in general, when the public support for any given bill is higher, the MPs are usually more likely to take it into consideration than if it lacks public support.

Public support was mentioned numerous times in the German Bundestag from both the supporting side, but it was acknowledged even by those who did not vote in favor due to other reasons. MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak in his speech mentioned public support as the reason to legalize it now, since over 80 % of the population supported it at the time when the debate was taking place (Luczak 2017, June 30). Connected to public support, we can also talk about the changing stances of Churches themselves about this matter. Some Churches both in Czechia and Germany are slowly changing their stance, and becoming more open to blessing same-sex couples. MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann mentions Churches in his statement:

“They will not be able to stay out of it because homosexual people live within them and because these people, who thankfully no longer wish to hide in our society, – not even in the churches – particularly in those places where love is the main topic and where faith in a boundless God is experienced as boundless in love as well.” - Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (February 18, 2016. Page 15274)

At the same time, in his follow-up argument he acknowledges that despite having said that, still, the situation is somewhat different for a party that has the word Christian in it (Kaufmann 2016, February 18). Other than that, MP Kaufmann shows that it might also be difficult for CDU/CSU to be in favor, because Germany is not fully secular, and the Church has an effect on the daily lives of citizens (Kaufmann 2016, February 18).

4.4.2 Reproduction is not the core of marriage

In Czechia, for most Christian Democrats according to their statements, it was reproduction that is the core of marriage. In Germany, there certainly had also been Christian Democratic MPs who agreed with that framing. On the other hand, there also were MPs who did not share the same view that reproduction is the core of marriage and therefore it being *the* deciding factor about who to allow to marry. The German MPs who did not see reproduction as the core of marriage mentioned other ideas what for them is the core of marriage, and among the most used possible cores of marriage was the *responsibility* for each other.

MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak frames his support in exactly this way, that the core of marriage for him is about being there for each other at all times, while adding that these values such as loyalty and responsibility are very conservative values (Luczak 2017, June 30). Again, showing that even a conservative party has the potential of being in favor of same-sex marriage when framing the support in certain ways. MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (2015, June 11) agrees with the notion that responsibility is the core of marriage. MP Kaufmann is not the only one who sees responsibility as the core of marriage. MP Dr. Heribert Hirte connects this frame with his religious beliefs, and he shares that he is not against, rather that he is in favor of same-sex marriage, because “*responsibility for each other, ... is in line with our Christian concept of humanity.*” (Hirte 2017, May 17. Page 23552).

4.4.3 Does not go against the Basic Law

Contrary to the positions of the opponents of same-sex marriage, there had been also some MPs who interpreted the German Basic Law (Constitution) in a way that same-sex marriage does not contradict it, therefore there is no need for amending the Constitution. MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak shares his perception of this:

“Do we need to amend our constitution for this? Personally, I don't think so. When we look at the constitutional definition of marriage in Article 6, paragraph 1 of our Basic Law, in the diction of the jurisprudence of our Federal Constitutional Court, we see that this concept is open. It must be embedded in the historical context. It must be interpreted in light of statutory regulations and societal views.” - Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak (June 30, 2017. Page 25112)

MP Kaufmann agrees and additionally brings in the frame *not a threat*, saying that it will not hurt anyone and there will be no decrease in childbirth and new marriages (as mentioned even before in this paper),

while also mentioning that gender in marriage is not talked about in the Grundgesetz (Kaufmann 2015, June 11).

From the interview that I have conducted with MP Jürgen Klimke, he also connects his support of the bill to this frame. He says that the Articles 1, 2 and especially the article 3 mean clear support of the proposal for him (Klimke in a personal interview, May 11, 2024). According to the Grundgesetz (Basic Law = Constitution), Article 1 states that *"The dignity of man is inviolable. To respect and protect it is the duty of all state authority."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 1, Para. 1). Article 2 says *"Everyone has the right to the free development of their personality, as long as they do not violate the rights of others and do not offend against the constitutional order or the moral law."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 2, Para. 1). And most importantly, Article 3 mentions that *"All people are equal before the law."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 3, Para. 1). Mr. Klimke therefore believes that all people should have the same rights and therefore must be treated as equal. He mentions that many people who work with him see it the same. (Klimke in a personal interview, May 11, 2024).

4.4.4 Meaning of marriage changes

In the past, there had been certain changes to marriage, as German MPs also expressed in their statements. As well as that the meaning of marriage varies from person to person. For many citizens and MPs, the core should be reproduction and therefore we should ensure that the status quo stays as it is. But on the other hand, for many people and MPs, the core of marriage is love or responsibility. Nowadays, when talking about same-sex partnerships, often, until learned otherwise, people think that they can get married, and therefore call them *married* from the beginning. This shows the change in the population's thinking, where a lot of people do not see marriage as only for one woman and one man, but instead, their perception is inclusive of same-sex couples. And certain MPs do notice it and reflect it in their statements too. We can see a slightly different (although still connected to this frame) approach that MP Peter Tauber used on his blog website (which he shared with me in our email conversation), where he explains in detail why he voted in favor. His approach describes that he remembers how in the past, progressive and left-wing parties did not like the institution of marriage and thought there was no need for it and it was "outdated", and nowadays it is exactly these actors who are calling for same-sex marriage (Tauber 2017). It can also be connected to the frame *"expansion of conservative ideas"* where it would mean that the progressive parties are embracing some conservative values and therefore expanding them.

But as far as statements coming directly from the Parliamentary debates, MP Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak and MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann frame their support in a way that mentions the changes.

“The understanding of marriage ... has fundamentally changed in recent years. In the past, there could be no marriage between nobility and commoners. In the past, there could be no marriage between Catholics and Protestants. In the past, a husband could terminate his wife’s employment without asking her. Nowadays, we have introduced the Civil Partnership Act. Nowadays, discriminatory regulations have been abolished. Today, same-sex couples are a natural part of our social reality. And nowadays, linguistically, there is no longer a distinction between being partnered and being married.” - Dr. Jan-Marco Luczak (June 30, 2017. Page 25112)

MP Dr. Stefan Kaufmann was able to bring his own experience with what I talked about above, because he himself entered a registered partnership with his husband.

“And by the way, in general parlance, two people of the same sex are considered married – not partnered. Incidentally, last year, almost all our well-wishers congratulated my husband Rolf and me on our wedding – not on our partnership. – Even from the CDU. – The word language recognition software (Word-Spracherkennung) doesn't recognize the word "partnered," even after 15 years of the civil partnership law.” Dr. Stefan Kaufmann (February 18, 2016. Page 15275)

CONCLUSION

In this paper, my main goal was to see whether the way German Christian Democratic MPs are framing their positions on same-sex marriage varies from the way Czech Christian Democratic MPs are framing theirs. And if it turns out to be that way, my goal was to see in which ways.

To provide myself with a certain starting point, I conducted a literature review, in which I looked at how the outside world used to frame their positions. This research gave me several frames (ways and topics of shaping their position) both in support and against same-sex marriage. Those who were supportive of same-sex marriage were using the frames *civil / human rights, equality, discrimination / tolerance / respect to other groups of citizens, separation of Church and state, not a threat, protection of the children, discrimination of a group, and expansion of conservative ideals*. On the other side, the opposing side to same-sex marriage was using frames such as *protection of children, lawlessness, slippery slope, religion, one man and one woman / history of marriage, reproduction as the core of marriage, and lack of public support*.

In my empirical part, where I was doing my own research, I looked at the speeches from both the Czech and the German Lower House (in Czechia it was the Chamber of Deputies, and in Germany, it was the Bundestag). From reading these speeches, I was able to sort out certain individual arguments into the already established frames. Since the literature review was mainly using frames from earlier times, certain new frames, both in Germany and Czechia, emerged, that were worth mentioning. These new ones against same-sex marriage are, in Czechia, *there is no right for marriage and no right for a child, equality without marriage, and the third way*. Since in Czechia, no Christian Democrat came forward in support of same-sex marriage, the new frames in favor are taken from the German Christian Democratic MPs, and those new frames are *public support, reproduction is not the core of marriage, does not go against the Basic Law and meaning of marriage changes*. By sorting the individual statements into these frames, I was able to see which ones were used more on the Czech side and neglected on the German side, or vice-versa. This brings me to the answers to my initial research questions.

1. Does the political discourse of the German Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU) regarding same-sex marriage differ somehow from their affiliate Czech Christian Democratic party (KDU-ČSL)?

It certainly does differ. Firstly, the main difference is that in Germany, we can find Christian Democratic MPs in the Lower House that held their speech supporting same-sex marriage. That is perhaps the biggest difference from the Czech Christian Democrats, where no MP shared their support. The speeches themselves also differed in ways of the language used. In the Czech case, lots of the speeches were revolving around the *slippery slope* frame, proposing possible scenarios that there are plans to redefine marriage to include more than just 2 people and so on. In the German case, the debate was more practical and was concentrated mainly on the *lawlessness* frame, where the MPs were discussing whether or not it was against the current Constitution. Speaking of other differences between the used frames, from my research it turns out that the Czech Christian Democrats were mainly focused on the frame of *protection of children*, where they say that a child needs both a feminine and a masculine role for the right development. The German Christian Democrats also used this frame, but in their case, focusing on the frame of *lawlessness* and the possible breaches of the Constitution were more significant. One notable framing that differentiates the 2 Christian Democratic parties is that among the supporters in the German CDU/CSU, there are mentions that the debate is not about the religious institution of marriage, but instead we are talking about the civil marriage, which means the Churches would not be “forced” to accept same-sex couples in marriages. This seems to be overlooked in the Czech discourse.

What these Christian Democratic parties in both countries had in common was their efforts to ensure some form of equality, but through a so-called *third way*. Another similarity is that the *historical* frame speaking about marriage as an institution of one woman and one man was heavily used in both countries. Regarding this, a difference occurred on the German side, where some MPs mentioned the frame *meaning of marriage changes*. Here they mentioned how many people already call same-sex partnerships *marriages*, and that love and responsibility are for many people the core of marriage, not reproduction.

Even the way the speeches are held in each country is slightly different. I noticed that in the Czech case, usually one person speaks, and if someone has a rebuttal to their statement, they wait and go share that (even a short sentence), after the first speaker is done. In Germany however, it was very common to see MPs who disagreed with the speaking MP, jumping in and expressing their disagreements vocally while the other person was speaking. Imagining a person who does not have a formed opinion about any given

topic, the German case of holding speeches gives the regular citizen both sides of the argument at the same time. While in Czechia, you usually only hear what one person is saying, therefore for any disagreements you have to actively look for it in another speech. Being able to hear both sides at the same time during one speech could in my opinion slightly affect the general opinion of the public.

Lastly, I find it interesting to point out, that researchers mention that after the legalization of same-sex marriage, even the Christian Democratic parties became more approving of it, as time went on. According to Jankowski (2022), there seems to be low resistance among candidates. This claim seems to be true, if I take into consideration even the situation regarding registered partnerships in Czechia. Before the legalization, the Czech Christian Democrats were mainly against it, but now it is completely different, and there is almost no resistance to registered partnerships. Instead, the resistance is now to same-sex marriage.

2. Considering the fact that quite a few CDU/CSU MPs voted in favor of same-sex marriage (Ehe für Alle), while KDU-ČSL MPs are against it, what are the reasons behind this difference?

This research question is partially already answered in the previous question. But the biggest difference to me is perhaps that in the German discourse, the MPs pointed out the distinction between the civil marriage and the religious marriage. And navigated the debate in the way that the discussion is about opening the civil institution of marriage to same-sex couples, and not forcing Churches to open the religious institution of marriage. This distinction was not very present, or maybe not at all, in the Czech discourse. It is possible that another reason for this difference is the presence of the LSU (Lesben und Schwule in der Union = lesbians and gays in the Union) organization within the German Christian Democratic party, which makes sure that the debate about LGBTQ rights does not fade.

From looking at the statements in the empirical part of this paper, it is also visible that the difference occurs also in the *religious* sphere, where in Germany, certain MPs are framing their support of same-sex marriage by explaining that according to their vision, love and responsibility for one another are conservative and Christian values. In Czechia, there were no such cases that would use the *religion* frame in support of same-sex marriage, despite Czechia being less religious than Christian Germany.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Abbott, Tony. 2013. TRANSCRIPT OF THE PRIME MINISTER THE HON. TONY ABBOTT MP, INTERVIEW WITH NEIL MITCHELL, RADIO 3AW, MELBOURNE Interview by Neil Mitchell.

https://parlinfo.aph.gov.au/parlInfo/download/media/pressrel/2798989/upload_binary/2798989.pdf;fileType=application%2Fpdf#search=%22media/pressrel/2798989%22. As cited in Grube, Dennis, and Elizabeth van Acker. 2016. “Rhetorically Defining a Social Institution: How Leaders Have Framed Same-Sex Marriage.” *Australian Journal of Political Science* 52 (2): 183–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2016.1260683>.

Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes, Beate Küpper, and Ulrich Klocke. 2017. “Einstellungen Gegenüber Lesben, Schwulen Und Bisexuellen in Deutschland.” Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes.

https://www.antidiskriminierungsstelle.de/SharedDocs/downloads/DE/publikationen/Umfragen/handout_themenjahrumfrage_2017.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4.

Bergner, Christoph. Email direct message to Karel Mařík. May 11, 2024.

Bělohávková, Romana. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065214.htm>¹

Bělohávková, Romana. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065215.htm>

Bělohávková, Romana. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 2. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065270.htm#r2>

¹ With certain speeches from the Czech Lower House of the Parliament, I created multiple references for the same day. This is because I wanted to provide the direct link that would lead directly to the part of the speech where the given MP stated what I mentioned in my paper

- Bělohávková, Romana. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 2. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065271.htm>
- Bělohávková, Romana. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070131.htm>
- Brandt, Helmut. 2015. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 11. Page 10441. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18109.pdf#P.10435>
- Brenner, Jochen. 2022. “Der Politiker-Professor – Heribert Hirte Im Porträt.” *Anwaltsblatt*. July 12, 2022. Accessed on May 10, 2024. <https://anwaltsblatt.anwaltverein.de/de/themen/kanzlei-praxis/der-politiker-professor-heribert-hirte-im-portraet>.
- Burr, Vivien. 2015. *Social Constructionism*. 3rd ed. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315715421>.
- Bush, George W. 2004. “President Calls for Constitutional Amendment Protecting Marriage.” Office of the Press Secretary. February 24. <https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/news/releases/2004/02/20040224-2.html>. As quoted in McFarland, Katherine. 2011. “Media Influence and Frame Diversity in the Debate over Same-Sex Marriage.” *The Communication Review* 14 (4): 255–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2011.624002>.
- Cameron, David. 2011. “David Cameron’s Conservative Conference Speech.” BBC. October 5. <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-politics-15189614>. As quoted in Grube, Dennis, and Elizabeth van Acker. 2016. “Rhetorically Defining a Social Institution: How Leaders Have Framed Same-Sex Marriage.” *Australian Journal of Political Science* 52 (2): 183–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2016.1260683>.
- Centrum pro výzkum veřejného mínění, Sociologický ústav AV ČR, v. v. i., Monika Kyselá, and Naděžda Čadová. 2023. “Tisková Zpráva Postoje Veřejnosti K Právům Homosexuálů -Duben/Květen 2023.” https://cvvm.soc.cas.cz/media/com_form2content/documents/c2/a5655/f9/ov230621.pdf
- Cullen, Simon. 2012. “Bernardi Resigns after Bestiality Comment.” *Www.abc.net.au*. September 19, 2012. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2012-09-19/controversy-over-cory-bernardi-bestiality-comments/4269604>.

- Čižmářová, Kristýna. 2023. “Analýza Rámování Registrovaného Partnerství v Politickém Diskurzu ČR.” Master’s thesis, Masarykova univerzita, Fakulta sociálních studií. https://is.muni.cz/th/wiegc/Cizmarova-Kristyna_DP.docx_.docx.
- ČTK. 2016. “Před 10 Lety Bylo v Česku Schváleno Registrované Partnerství.” Deník.cz, March 15, 2016. Accessed May 10, 2024. https://www.denik.cz/z_domova/pred-10-lety-bylo-v-cesku-schvaleno-registrovane-partnerstvi-20160314.html.
- ČTK. 2024. “Sněmovna Schválila pro Stejnopohlavní Páry Partnerství S Většinou Práv Manželů | ČeskéNoviny.cz.” Www.ceskenoviny.cz. February 28, 2024. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.ceskenoviny.cz/zpravy/2485224>.
- Deutsches Bundestag. 2017. “Deutscher Bundestag - Namentliche Abstimmungen.” Deutscher Bundestag. July 30, 2017. <https://www.bundestag.de/parlament/plenum/abstimmung/abstimmung/?id=486>.
- Dufek, Aleš. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, May 31. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065198.htm#r2>
- Dufek, Aleš. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065208.htm#r2>
- Dufek, Aleš. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 2. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065269.htm#r2>
- Dufek, Aleš. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070117.htm#r3>
- Egale. 2001a. *Egale’s Factum to the Ontario Court in the Ontario Marriage Challenge (Amended Factum of the Intervener)*. Ontario Superior Court of Justice (Division Court), October 12. as cited in Smith, Miriam. 2007. “Framing Same-Sex Marriage in Canada and the United States: Goodridge, Halpern and the National Boundaries of Political Discourse.” *Social & Legal Studies* 16 (1): 5–26. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0964663907073444>.

Egelko, Bob. "Same-sex marriage case goes to judge." *San Francisco Chronicle*, June 17, 2010, p. A1. As quoted in Warren, Deirdre M., and Katrina R. Bloch. 2014. "Framing Same-Sex Marriage: Media Constructions of California's Proposition 8." *The Social Science Journal* 51 (4): 503–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2014.06.011>.²

Euronews, and AFP. 2022. "Slovenia Legalises Same-Sex Marriage and Adoption." Euronews. October 4, 2022. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.euronews.com/2022/10/04/slovenia-becomes-first-east-european-country-to-legalise-same-sex-marriage-and-adoption>.

Fiala, Jan. 2023. "Stejnopohlavní Svazky v Českém Politickém Diskurzu." Master's thesis, Vysoká škola CEVRO Institut, Politologie a mezinárodní vztahy. https://is.vsci.cz/th/uc50v/J._Fiala_-_manzelstvi_Archive.pdf?kod=d163566;lang=en.

Fritzsche, Christopher, und Juliane Lang. 2019. „„Ein Papa, Eine Mama, Ganz einfach!“: Eine Hegemonietheoretische Analyse Der Gegnerschaft Zur ‚Ehe für alle‘“. *PROKLA. Zeitschrift für Kritische Sozialwissenschaft* 49 (197). Berlin, DE:515-31. <https://doi.org/10.32387/prokla.v49i197.1843>.

Goffman, Erving. 1974. *Frame Analysis: An Essay on the Organization of Experience*. Boston Northeastern University Press. As cited in McFarland, Katherine. 2011. "Media Influence and Frame Diversity in the Debate over Same-Sex Marriage." *The Communication Review* 14 (4): 255–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2011.624002>.

Golasowská, Pavla. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070129.htm>

Golasowská, Pavla. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070130.htm>

Golasowská, Pavla. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070129.htm>

² Unfortunately (as of the day of writing), for this specific statement by Bob Egelko in the *San Francisco Chronicle*, I was not able to find the original source that Warren and Bloch (2014) mention in their paper. However, I took the information from their Bibliography, and changed the style to Chicago, using ChatGPT.

- Grube, Dennis, and Elizabeth van Acker. 2016. "Rhetorically Defining a Social Institution: How Leaders Have Framed Same-Sex Marriage." *Australian Journal of Political Science* 52 (2): 183–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2016.1260683>.
- Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland*. 1949. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.bundestag.de/gg>.
- Hall, Dylan, Sadie Culp, Daniel Rios Poli, and Frank Baumgartner. 2019. "Framing Marriage Equality." https://fbaum.unc.edu/teaching/POLI421_Fa19/papers/MarriageEquality.pdf.
- Hasselfeldt, Gerda. 2017. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 30. Page 25114. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18244.pdf#P.25105>
- Hatalsky, Lanae Erickson, and Sarah Trumble. "How Marriage Won in Washington State." *Third Way*, 2012. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep34303>. As cited in Adam, Erin M., and Betsy L. Cooper. 2017. "Equal Rights vs. Special Rights: Rights Discourses, Framing, and Lesbian and Gay Antidiscrimination Policy in Washington State." *Law & Social Inquiry* 42 (03): 830–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lsi.12229>.
- Heller, Šimon. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 2. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065272.htm>
- Heller, Šimon. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070118.htm#r14>
- Hirte, Heribert. 2017. Warum CDU-Abgeordneter Hirte für "Ehe für alle" stimmte Interview by Renardo Schlegelmilch. Domradio.de. Accessed on May 10, 2024. <https://www.domradio.de/artikel/warum-cdu-abgeordneter-hirte-fuer-ehe-fuer-alle-stimmte>.
- Hirte, Heribert Dr. 2017. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, May 17. Page 23552. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18233.pdf#P.23550>
- Hirte, Heribert. 2021. Heribert Hirte (CDU): Ehemalige Werteunion hat hohen Einfluss in Kölner CDU Interview by Christoph Heinemann. Deutschlandfunk. Accessed on May 10, 2024.

<https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/listen-zur-bundestagswahl-heribert-hirte-cdu-ehemalige-100.html>.

Hoffmann, Alexander. 2015. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 11. Page 10448, 10449. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18109.pdf#P.10435>

Hoffmann, Alexander. 2016. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, November 10. Page 19900, 19901. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18199.pdf#P.19893>

Hoffmann, Alexander. 2017. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, May 17. Page 23555, 23556. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18233.pdf#P.23550>

Hull, Kathleen E. 2001. "THE POLITICAL LIMITS of the RIGHTS FRAME: THE CASE of SAME-SEX MARRIAGE in HAWAII." *Sociological Perspectives* 44 (2): 207–32. <https://doi.org/10.1525/sop.2001.44.2.207>.

Jankowski, Michael. 2022. "Slowly Adopting: The Impact of Same-Sex Marriage Legalisation on the Attitudes of Parliamentary Candidates in Germany." *European Journal of Politics and Gender* XX (XX): 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1332/251510821x16612491304936>.

Jílková, Marie. 2023. PROMĚNÁM SVĚTA NEZABRÁNÍME Interview by Andrea Procházková. Accessed on May 10, 2024. <https://www.respekt.cz/tydenik/2023/25/promenam-sveta-nezabranime>.

Johnson, Tyler. 2012. "Equality, Morality, and the Impact of Media Framing: Explaining Opposition to Same-Sex Marriage and Civil Unions." *Politics & Policy* 40 (6): 1053–80. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-1346.2012.00398.x>.

Jurečka, Marian. 2024. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, February 7. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/092schuz/s092061.htm#r4>

Kania, Ursula. 2019. "Marriage for All ('Ehe Fuer Alle')?! A Corpus-Assisted Discourse Analysis of the Marriage Equality Debate in Germany." *Critical Discourse Studies* 17 (2): 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405904.2019.1656656>.

- Kauder, Björn, and Niklas Potrafke. 2018. "Warum Stimmen Unionsabgeordnete Für Die Ehe Für Alle? Es Ist Die Konkurrenz Im Wahlkreis!" Ifo Schnelldienst 71 (24): 26–27. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/198699>.
- Kauder, Björn , and Niklas Potrafke. 2021. "Im Zeitgeist? Wähler Belohnen Unionsabgeordnete Für Die Unterstützung Der Ehe Für Alle." Ifo Schnelldienst 74 (08): 21–23. <https://www.ifo.de/publikationen/2021/aufsatz-zeitschrift/test-im-zeitgeist-waehler-belohnen-unionsabgeordnete-fuer>.
- Kauder, Volker. 2017. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 30. Page 25107. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18244.pdf#P.25105>
- Kaufmann, Stefan Dr. 2015. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 11. Page 10446, 10447. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18109.pdf#P.10435>
- Kaufmann, Stefan Dr. 2016. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, February 18. Page 15274, 15275, 15276. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18155.pdf#P.15273>
- Klimke, Jürgen. Interview by Karel Mařík. Zoom, May 11, 2024.
- Kukla, André. 2000. *Social Constructivism and the Philosophy of Science*. London: Routledge. As cited in Kim, Beaumie. 2001. "Social Constructivism." In *Emerging Perspectives on Learning, Teaching, and Technology*.
- Lebenspartnerschaft.de. n.d. "Unterschied Ehe Und Eingetragene Lebenspartnerschaft." www.lebenspartnerschaft.de. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.lebenspartnerschaft.de/unterschied-ehe-und-eingetragene-lebenspartnerschaft.html#:~:text=Eine%20eingetragene%20Lebenspartnerschaft%20konnte%20von.>
- Liebler, Carol M., Joseph Schwartz, and Todd Harper. 2009. "Queer Tales of Morality: The Press, Same-Sex Marriage, and Hegemonic Framing." *Journal of Communication* 59 (4): 653–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2009.01451.x>.

- Luczak, Jan-Marco Dr. 2017. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 30. Page 25111, 25112. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18244.pdf#P.25105>
- Machová, Martina. 2021. “Jednota Nové Koalice Pirátů a STAN Má Svou Mez: Manželství pro Všechny.” Seznam Zprávy. January 16, 2021. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.seznamzpravy.cz/clanek/jednota-nove-koalice-piratu-a-stan-ma-svou-mez-manzelstvi-pro-vsechny-137301>.
- McFarland, Katherine. 2011. “Media Influence and Frame Diversity in the Debate over Same-Sex Marriage.” *The Communication Review* 14 (4): 255–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2011.624002>.
- Navrátil, Jiří. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070157.htm>
- Nelson, Thomas E., and Donald R. Kinder. 1996. “Issue Frames and Group-Centrism in American Public Opinion.” *The Journal of Politics* 58 (4): 1055–78. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2960149>. As quoted in Gainous, Jason, and Laurie Rhodebeck. 2016. “Is Same-Sex Marriage an Equality Issue? Framing Effects among African Americans.” *Journal of Black Studies* 47 (7): 682–700. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021934716642590>
- Nováková, Nina. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065212.htm#r8>
- Nováková, Nina. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065213.htm>
- Nováková, Nina. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070133.htm>
- Obama, Barack. 2015. “Remarks by the President on the Supreme Court Decision on Marriage Equality.” The White House, Office of the Press Secretary. June 26. <https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/the-press-office/2015/06/26/remarks-president-supreme-court-decision-marriage-equality>. As quoted in Grube, Dennis, and Elizabeth van Acker. 2016. “Rhetorically Defining a Social Institution: How Leaders Have Framed Same-Sex

Marriage.” *Australian Journal of Political Science* 52 (2): 183–98.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2016.1260683>.

Okamura, Hayato. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065208.htm#r4>

Okamura, Hayato. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 29. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/070schuz/s070119.htm#r4>

Omsted, Alden. 2008. “Court Ruling Led to Prop. 8 Mess.” SFGATE. November 7, 2008. <https://www.sfgate.com/opinion/article/Court-ruling-led-to-Prop-8-mess-3186526.php>. As quoted in Warren, Deirdre M., and Katrina R. Bloch. 2014. “Framing Same-Sex Marriage: Media Constructions of California’s Proposition 8.” *The Social Science Journal* 51 (4): 503–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2014.06.011>.³

Pavlovský, Jakub. 2018. “Kampaň Za Stejnopohlavní Manželství v ČR a Její Prezentace v Českých Online Médiiích.” Bachelor thesis, Univerzita Karlova, Fakulta sociálních věd. <https://dspace.cuni.cz/bitstream/handle/20.500.11956/99390/130229316.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.

Pekarová Adamová, Markéta (@market_a). 2024. "Poslanecký klub @TOP09cz podpoří svými hlasy “manželství pro všechny”. Je nejvyšší čas, aby se srovnala práva. Zároveň moc prosím, aby se debata vedla kultivovaně a nestala se nástrojem vyvolávání strachu a nenávisti. Častokrát jsme byli na plénu sněmovny svědky zraňujících slov. Nedopusťme to. Twitter, February 6, 2024, 12:24PM. Accessed May 10, 2024. https://x.com/market_a/status/1754828404359340114.

Perrin, Andrew J. 2006. *Citizen Speak*. University of Chicago Press. As cited in McFarland, Katherine. 2011. “Media Influence and Frame Diversity in the Debate over Same-Sex Marriage.” *The Communication Review* 14 (4): 255–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2011.624002>.

³ For this particular statement by Alden Omsted, I originally saw it in Warren and Bloch (2014). However, as of the date of writing, I unfortunately was not able to access the source they got this statement from. I managed to find the same statement on a different website, which is SFGATE, that I mention in my Bibliography. In Warren and Bloch’s (2014) Bibliography, it is mentioned as follows: Olmsted, A. (2008, November 7). *Democracy thwarted*. San Francisco Chronicle

- Pizmony-Levy, Oren, and Aaron Ponce. 2013. "Framing Strategies and Public Support for the Legalization of Marriage between Two People of the Same Sex." *Sociological Perspectives* 56 (2): 169–90. <https://doi.org/10.1525/sop.2013.56.2.169>.
- Silberhorn, Alexander. 2013. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, December 19. Page 302. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18006.pdf#P.300>
- Sherkat, Darren E., Melissa Powell-Williams, Gregory Maddox, and Kylan Mattias de Vries. 2011. "Religion, Politics, and Support for Same-Sex Marriage in the United States, 1988–2008." *Social Science Research* 40 (1): 167–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2010.08.009> as cited in Colistra, Rita, and Chelsea Betts Johnson. 2019. "Framing the Legalization of Marriage for Same-Sex Couples: An Examination of News Coverage Surrounding the U.S. Supreme Court's Landmark Decision." *Journal of Homosexuality* 68 (1): 88–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2019.1627128>.
- Sniderman, Paul M., and Sean M. Theriault. 2004. "CHAPTER 5: The Structure of Political Argument and the Logic of Issue Framing." *Studies in Public Opinion*, December, 133–65. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780691188386-007>. As cited in McFarland, Katherine. 2011. "Media Influence and Frame Diversity in the Debate over Same-Sex Marriage." *The Communication Review* 14 (4): 255–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2011.624002>.
- Snow, David, and Robert Benford. 1992. "Master Frames and Cycles of Protest." *Frontier in Social Movement Theory*, January, 133–55. as quoted in Ghoshal, Raj. 2009. "Argument Forms, Frames, and Value Conflict: Persuasion in the Case of Same-Sex Marriage." *Cultural Sociology* 3 (1): 76–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1749975508100672>
- Spieker, Manfred. 2015. "Auf Eigene Kinder Ausgerichtet." *Junge Freiheit*. July 24, 2015. <https://jungefreiheit.de/kultur/2015/auf-eigene-kinder-ausgerichtet/>. As quoted in Fritzsche, Christopher, and Juliane Lang. 2019. "„Ein Papa, Eine Mama, Ganz Einfach!“." *PROKLA. Zeitschrift Für Kritische Sozialwissenschaft* 49 (197): 515–31. <https://doi.org/10.32387/prokla.v49i197.1843>.
- Sütterlin-Waack, Sabine Dr. 2016. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, November 10. Page 19897. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18199.pdf#P.19893>

- Tauber, Peter. 2017. "Die Ehe Ist Ein Äußerliches, Weltlich Ding...." Schwarzer Peter (blog). July 29, 2017. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://blog.petertauber.de/?p=3100>.
- Ulbert, Cornelia. 2014. "Social Constructivism." In *Theories of International Relations*. London: Routledge.
- Ulrich, Volker Dr. 2016. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, February 18. Page 15279. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18155.pdf#P.15273>
- Výborný, Marek. 2023. Speech, Poslanecká Sněmovna Parlamentu České republiky, June 1. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://www.psp.cz/eknih/2021ps/stenprot/065schuz/s065215.htm#r8>
- Warren, Deirdre M., and Katrina R. Bloch. 2014. "Framing Same-Sex Marriage: Media Constructions of California's Proposition 8." *The Social Science Journal* 51 (4): 503–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2014.06.011>. As cited in Colistra, Rita, and Chelsea Betts Johnson. 2019. "Framing the Legalization of Marriage for Same-Sex Couples: An Examination of News Coverage Surrounding the U.S. Supreme Court's Landmark Decision." *Journal of Homosexuality* 68 (1): 88–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2019.1627128>.
- Weinberg, Marcus. 2015. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 11. Page 10450-10451. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18109.pdf#P.10435>
- Winkelmeier-Becker, Elisabeth. 2013. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, December 19. Page 307, 308. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18006.pdf#P.300>
- Winkelmeier-Becker, Elisabeth. 2015. Speech, Deutscher Bundestag, June 11. Page 10437. Accessed May 10, 2024. <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/18/18109.pdf#P.10435>
- Zheng, Yue, and Lik Sam Chan. 2020. "Framing Same-Sex Marriage in U.S. Liberal and Conservative Newspapers from 2004 to 2016: Changes in Issue Attributes, Organizing Themes, and Story Tones." *The Social Science Journal*, February, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2019.07.001>.

ANNEXES

Personal statements and sources directly from the MPs

Jürgen Klimke (CDU, Hamburg)

I managed to get in contact and establish a Zoom meeting with Jürgen Klimke, who used to be a Member of the German Bundestag until 2017, representing the CDU. Keeping in mind the frames from my literature review and the results from the comparative analysis, I was curious to dive deeper and see how it was perceived firsthand. Mr. Klimke voted in favor of same-sex marriage along with 74 other CDU/CSU colleagues. The questions that I was able to ask Mr. Klimke were:

1. What is the reasoning behind your vote? Have you always supported same-sex marriage, or has there been a certainly framed argument that changed your position?

- For Mr. Klimke, his position on same-sex marriage goes back to the Grundgesetz (German Basic Law = Constitution), which is celebrating 75 years this year (2024). The focus for him goes towards the Article 1, Article 2, but mainly towards Article 3.
 - Article 1 states that *"The dignity of man is inviolable. To respect and protect it is the duty of all state authority."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 1, Para. 1)
 - Article 2 says *"Everyone has the right to the free development of their personality, as long as they do not violate the rights of others and do not offend against the constitutional order or the moral law."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 1, Para. 1)
 - And most importantly, Article 3 mentions *"All people are equal before the law."* (Grundgesetz, Art. 1, Para. 1). Mr. Klimke therefore believes that all people should have the same rights and therefore have to be treated as equal. He mentions that many people who work with him see it the same.

2. Do you have an idea about other reasons why some CDU/CSU MPs voted in favor and some voted against?

- It makes a difference whether one looks at Ehe für Alle in a legal, political or Christian lens. And for many people, it is based on their Catholic faith. Another point is whether the question is looked at as the state (civil) institution of marriage, or the Church institution of marriage.

3. What frames of arguments do you think were the ones that were able to persuade some of the MPs to either vote in favor or against?

- Often MPs decide based on the Basic Law, whether or not it contradicts it, according to their interpretation. Another indicator of how an MP is going to vote is the constituency they represent. He mentioned that it is seen differently in Northern Germany, and in Southern Germany. The region often might play a role in the final decision of the individual MP.
- Another note-worthy factor is that constituencies are made according to their size, so there might be a difference in the vote between an MP who represents a big city, such as MP Klimke in Hamburg, and in the vote of an MP in rural Bavaria.
- Mr. Klimke mentioned that responsibility for the constituency is another factor. Often the *fear* of losing votes and the seat in some more conservative constituencies is what makes certain MPs vote against, even if they personally are in favor of same-sex marriage. Because they are elected to represent their voters.

4. Which frame do you personally think was the most widely used one in the debate in Germany? (As an example, I read in one of the interviews with you that the discussion is about civil marriage, not Church marriage. And I have not heard this many times in the Czech discourse - maybe never)

- According to MP Jürgen Klimke, usually, when the debate is about same-sex marriage, we are talking about the civil marriage more than the religious one. That leads to framing the arguments in a more practical and technical way (inheritance, adoption of children) and in some debates, the religious framing becomes less visible.

5. Could Direktmandat in Germany be in your opinion one of the reasons why the voting behavior of the 2 Christian Democratic parties (German CDU/CSU and the Czech KDU-ČSL) differs? (We do not have such voting in Czechia, therefore the individual positions of the MPs do not matter too much, mostly the party) - This would mean that CDU/CSU is trying to appeal to voters who are more progressive, so they do not lose to FDP or even left-wing parties?

- Mr. Klimke believes that it can be the case, because how a political party appears and presents itself can affect how voters behave. Meaning in Catholic regions of Germany, such as Bavaria, as an example, if they elect an MP who is gay, it might happen that despite the fact that his opinion might be different, he might vote against or abstain from the vote.
- On the other hand, from Mr. Klimke's previous constituency, Hamburg, if a candidate from a big city does not support same-sex marriage, people will show their disapproval at the polls and instead elect someone who would represent their views in support of same-sex marriage. This means that it really depends on what constituency you are representing. Your stance can be supported in one constituency and rejected in another, even within the same country.

6. If you have any idea, from your perspective, what could be the reason for the difference in the voting result (CDU/CSU voting somewhat in favor, KDU voting against)?

- From the inputs by Mr. Klimke, one of the reasons for the difference could be that in CDU, there is an LGBTQ organization within the party, called LSU (in English: Lesbian and Gay Union). Having this organization within the party can certainly influence if and how the internal debate within the party will take place. It makes sure that the discussion does not, according to Mr. Klimke, stay "*somewhere in the dark room.*" The Czech Christian Democrats do not have an official LGBTQ organization in their party, therefore there is no united body that would have a chance to influence the debate. The Czech KDU-ČSL does have its youth wing, and also MPs and members that are not heterosexual, but no LGBTQ body within the party itself steering the conversation.

7. Do you think CDU/CSU is more liberal than KDU? If so, would that explain the differences? (It is talked about that CSU is very conservative, but yet some MPs voted in favor of same-sex marriage)

- He is not sure about KDU-ČSL, but regarding CDU and CSU, the Christian Social Union is more conservative than the Christian Democratic Union. But they are sister parties and listen to each other and value each other's opinions. But from my perspective, since they are running together in the elections, it is likely that CDU, being more liberal, is in certain aspects able to persuade CSU to adjust their views. Or vice-versa.

- One interesting thing Mr. Klimke mentioned is that him being someone who has been married for 40 years, has 4 children and 8 grandchildren, and recognizes the LSU, his support for same-sex marriage can be seen as more credible and convincing to some voters who are similar in these aspects of life.

8. Is religion one of the reasons for the difference (or Catholicism/Protestantism)? Or is it the level of conservatism the party wants to maintain?

- Religion can certainly make a difference. When it comes to the German parties, MP Klimke mentioned that the German Catholic Church is consistent in its opposition to same-sex marriage. And CSU in many aspects accepts the positions of the Catholic Church. Whereas the CDU is more leaning towards the Evangelical Church (but with links to the Catholic Church too), and divides politics and religion more than CSU does. Unlike the CSU, the CDU does not have the pressure coming from the Church to align with views, but rather they have an open dialogue. This can partially explain the reason why a higher share of CDU MPs voted in favor than CSU MPs.

9. Do you think the bill passed, because SPD, FDP and Greens ruled out making a coalition with CDU/CSU unless it passes? Or was that mostly irrelevant?

- Contrary to my expectations, Mr. Klimke does not see that as the decisive factor. Instead, he mentions that it was the decision within the party, not done through external pushes such as coalition-making.

(Jürgen Klimke, via Zoom call with Karel Mařík, May 11, 2024)

Heribert Hirte (CDU, Cologne II.)

I managed to get in touch with Mr. Hirte via email, where after I asked him questions, he provided me with a link to his website, Twitter profile, his Facebook profile, and also interviews with him, where I was able to understand the reasons behind his vote. MP Dr. Heribert Hirte managed to win his seat through Direktmandat (Brenner 2022) and he voted in favor of same-sex marriage in Germany. This allowed him to be elected through Direktmandat in 2017 again, but brought him problems in his local CDU cell in Cologne, due to not being conservative enough, according to the wishes of the local politicians (Hirte 2021).

Shortly regarding an interview that domradio.de conducted with him, he mentions that, as other MPs mentioned in their speeches, and mentions that we should allow same-sex couples to get married out of respect for each person (Hirte 2017) (therefore using the *tolerance and respect frame* from this paper), and by not doing so, it is hurting people, which he sees as wrong (Hirte 2017). MP Hirte in his argumentation also uses the *religious frame* and adds that he supports opening marriage to same-sex couples, because it is the right thing to do “*under the Christian view of humanity*”, as MP Hirte says (Hirte 2017). Still using the religious frame, he also supports same-sex marriage because he believes that God accepts people as they are, and that responsibility for each other is a Christian idea of marriage (Hirte 2017). To this he adds that it is conservative to have these values (Hirte 2017), therefore he takes on the *expansion of conservative ideals* frame as well in his argument.

As well as Mr. Klimke said it, Mr. Hirte is among those who believe that there is a distinction to be made in the debate, and that is that we are talking about civil marriage, not religious marriage (Hirte 2017).

Peter Tauber (CDU, Main-Kinzig-Wetterau, Schotten)

MP Peter Tauber was another Christian Democratic MP who was so kind to respond to my questions and gave me a link to his website where he explains his position. From his blog, I found really interesting his input, where he mentions that he remembers how in the past, progressive and left-wing parties did not like the institution of marriage and thought there was no need for it and it was “outdated”, and nowadays it is exactly these actors who are calling for same-sex marriage. (Tauber 2017). This is directly connected to the frame *meaning of marriage changes*, showing that the previously rather conservative idea is now more mainstream. This brings me to another link to another frame that is connected to it, the *expansion of conservative ideals*.

Regarding the *religious* frame, he is in favor and explains it from his Protestant point of view, saying that for Catholics, marriage is a Holy Sacrament. On the contrary, for Protestants, it is not. (Tauber 2017).

Christoph Bergner (CDU, Halle)

Christoph Bergner is among those who voted against the proposal for same-sex marriage. His reasoning was not connected to the *religious* frame, but instead, it was connected to the *lawlessness* frame. To be more specific, he belonged to the large group of CDU/CSU MPs who were worried about whether the proposal is in accordance with the Constitution (Grundgesetz = Basic Law) (Christoph Bergner, email

direct message to Karel Mařík, March 3, 2024). He too mentioned the Article 6 which puts marriage and family under the protection of the state (Grundgesetz, Art. 6, Para. 1) (Christoph Bergner, email direct message to Karel Mařík, March 3, 2024). When talking about the possible reasons for differences in voting behavior among the German Christian Democrats, he mentions the different interpretations of the German Constitution, primarily about the word *marriage* in the Article 6. He explains, as other MPs mentioned too, that the only correct way how it could have been legalized is through the change of the Constitution, not just amending the Civil Law Code.

(Christoph Bergner, via email direct message to Karel Mařík, March 3, 2024).

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to compare if (or how) the Christian Democratic party discourse differs in Germany and Czechia. The motivation for this research is the fact that same-sex marriage passed in Germany in 2017 with the help of the governing CDU/CSU but did not pass in Czechia in 2024 when KDU-ČSL was in the government (no MP is in favor). In connection to the social constructivist IR school, I am using framing theory to conduct this comparative discourse analysis, with the focus on qualitative data, mainly coming from speeches in the Lower Houses of the Parliaments in both countries. Based on the literature review, I have listed several possible ways of framing, which were later in my empirical part mentioned more closely, specifically in regard to how the MPs were talking about same-sex marriage in their speeches. In this paper, I am also bringing new data directly from a personal communication (Zoom meeting and email communication) with some German MPs who voted in favor, with their reasoning and their perception of the examined situation. The results showed that there in fact was a difference in framing between the two Christian Democratic parties (that is closely mentioned in the paper), which could have contributed to the different outcomes in legalization. The main difference, however, is that unlike in Germany, in Czechia there was no Christian Democratic MP who voted in favor of same-sex marriage.

Keywords: Same-sex marriage, Marriage equality, Czechia, Germany, LGBTQ